

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Estrone

CHID: 22367 CASRN: 53-16-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J11

M4ID: 30008988

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.29 MAX_MED: 0.821 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Androstene-3,17-dione

CHID: 24523 CASRN: 63-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N10

M4ID: 30009083

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1 MAX_MED: 0.773 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethomorph

CHID: 34545 CASRN: 110488-70-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I22

M4ID: 30008975

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.85 MAX_MED: 1.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tebufenozide

CHID: 34948 CASRN: 112410-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C03

M4ID: 30008511

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.88 MAX_MED: 2.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Testosterone propionate

CHID: 36515 CASRN: 57-85-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C07

M4ID: 30008455

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.64 MAX_MED: 2.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acetaminophen

CHID: 20006 CASRN: 103-90-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P21

M4ID: 30008766

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	506.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.23 MAX_MED: 4.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acifluorfen

CHID: 20022 CASRN: 50594-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J03

M4ID: 30008980

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	493.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.66 MAX_MED: 1.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Allantoin

CHID: 20043 CASRN: 97-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P11

M4ID: 30008756

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	607.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.7 MAX_MED: 7.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Amitrole

CHID: 20076 CASRN: 61-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078020

M4ID: 30008559

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	532.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.15 MAX_MED: 5.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Aniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20091 CASRN: 142-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L10

M4ID: 30008641

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	500.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.44 MAX_MED: -0.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Methoxyaniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20093 CASRN: 20265-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G07

M4ID: 30008329

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	459.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 3.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Aspartame

CHID: 20107 CASRN: 22839-47-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K12

M4ID: 30009013

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	539.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.11 MAX_MED: 2.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Aspirin

CHID: 20108 CASRN: 50-78-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D13

M4ID: 30008425

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.16 MAX_MED: 4.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Atrazine
 CHID: 20112 CASRN: 1912-24-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N11
 M4ID: 30009084

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	525.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.83 MAX_MED: 3.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Auramine hydrochloride

CHID: 20114 CASRN: 2465-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J09

M4ID: 30008690

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	601.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.563 MAX_MED: 0.513 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium azide

CHID: 20121 CASRN: 26628-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D11

M4ID: 30008844

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.18 MAX_MED: 7.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Azinphos-methyl

CHID: 20122 CASRN: 86-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B19

M4ID: 30008467

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	550.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.49 MAX_MED: 6.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine

CHID: 20127 CASRN: 30516-87-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L14

M4ID: 30009039

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	451.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00238 MAX_MED: 0.466 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzidine

CHID: 20137 CASRN: 92-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G13

M4ID: 30008323

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.06 MAX_MED: 2.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium benzoate

CHID: 20140 CASRN: 532-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K11

M4ID: 30008664

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.77 MAX_MED: 4.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,3-Benzofuran

CHID: 20141 CASRN: 271-89-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D21

M4ID: 30008854

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	368.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.74 MAX_MED: 1.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzoic acid

CHID: 20143 CASRN: 65-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G12

M4ID: 30008324

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.82 MAX_MED: 5.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2,3-Benzotriazole

CHID: 20147 CASRN: 95-14-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N21

M4ID: 30008582

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	380.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.86 MAX_MED: 2.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzyl acetate

CHID: 20151 CASRN: 140-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D23

M4ID: 30008415

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	397.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.47 MAX_MED: 2.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzyl alcohol

CHID: 20152 CASRN: 100-51-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N07

M4ID: 30008596

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	498.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.1 MAX_MED: 4.36 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bis(2-chloroethyl) ether

CHID: 20168 CASRN: 111-44-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K03

M4ID: 30008672

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.14 MAX_MED: 1.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-tert-butylphenol

CHID: 20212 CASRN: 2409-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078002

M4ID: 30008577

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	639.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.27 MAX_MED: 3.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Butyrolactone

CHID: 20224 CASRN: 96-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N12

M4ID: 30008367

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.61 MAX_MED: 1.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Caffeine

CHID: 20232 CASRN: 58-08-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K18

M4ID: 30008657

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.72 MAX_MED: 4.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Chloro-4-nitrobenzene

CHID: 20281 CASRN: 100-00-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B05

M4ID: 30008481

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.16 MAX_MED: 4.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Chloro-4-methylaniline

CHID: 20286 CASRN: 95-74-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F09

M4ID: 30008381

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	417.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.286 MAX_MED: 0.0222 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloroaniline

CHID: 20295 CASRN: 106-47-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H15

M4ID: 30008944

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	420.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.923 MAX_MED: 1.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Monuron

CHID: 20311 CASRN: 150-68-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J12

M4ID: 30008687

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.02 MAX_MED: 5.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Citric acid

CHID: 20332 CASRN: 77-92-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H23

M4ID: 30008724

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	373.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.546 MAX_MED: 0.511 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Coumaphos

CHID: 20347 CASRN: 56-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K21

M4ID: 30009022

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.4 MAX_MED: 2.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline

CHID: 20350 CASRN: 120-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E10

M4ID: 30008867

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.23	MAX_MED:	1.1	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanone

CHID: 20359 CASRN: 108-94-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I17

M4ID: 30008706

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	450.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.8 MAX_MED: 3.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene
 CHID: 20409 CASRN: 53-70-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H04
 M4ID: 30008743

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	551.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.39 MAX_MED: 3.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propyzamide

CHID: 20420 CASRN: 23950-58-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K12

M4ID: 30008663

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	528.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.29 MAX_MED: 5.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dichlone

CHID: 20425 CASRN: 117-80-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E09

M4ID: 30008405

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.305 MAX_MED: 0.372 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 20431 CASRN: 106-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091014

M4ID: 30008341

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.37 MAX_MED: 1.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dichlorprop

CHID: 20440 CASRN: 120-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B13

M4ID: 30008473

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	469.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.32 MAX_MED: 3.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dichlorvos

CHID: 20449 CASRN: 62-73-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D14

M4ID: 30008847

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3 MAX_MED: 3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl hydrogen phosphite

CHID: 20493 CASRN: 868-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J19

M4ID: 30008996

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.8 MAX_MED: 3.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 20494 CASRN: 756-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M20

M4ID: 30009069

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.02 MAX_MED: 2.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethylaminoethanol
CHID: 20505 CASRN: 108-01-0
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H24
M4ID: 30008953

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	417.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.07 MAX_MED: 2.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylaniline

CHID: 20507 CASRN: 121-69-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E08

M4ID: 30008406

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	592.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.41 MAX_MED: 7.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,1-Dimethylhydrazine
 CHID: 20516 CASRN: 57-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H06
 M4ID: 30008741

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	509.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.65 MAX_MED: 5.45 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20529 CASRN: 121-14-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L02

M4ID: 30009027

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	372.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.13 MAX_MED: 2.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium erythorbate (1:1)

CHID: 20570 CASRN: 6381-77-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H14

M4ID: 30008943

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.439 MAX_MED: -0.144 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethylene glycol

CHID: 20597 CASRN: 107-21-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D22

M4ID: 30008416

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.86 MAX_MED: 6.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Vinyl-1-cyclohexene dioxide

CHID: 20604 CASRN: 106-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078006

M4ID: 30008573

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.39 MAX_MED: 5.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 20605 CASRN: 104-76-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078021

M4ID: 30008558

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	373.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1 MAX_MED: 1.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Eugenol

CHID: 20617 CASRN: 97-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K17

M4ID: 30008658

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.13 MAX_MED: 3.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Finasteride

CHID: 20625 CASRN: 98319-26-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D22

M4ID: 30008855

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.62 MAX_MED: 1.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluometuron
 CHID: 20628 CASRN: 2164-17-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078012
 M4ID: 30008567

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.25 MAX_MED: 6.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5-Fluorouracil

CHID: 20634 CASRN: 51-21-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I02

M4ID: 30008955

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	383.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.81 MAX_MED: 2.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Glycidol

CHID: 20666 CASRN: 556-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N20

M4ID: 30008583

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	496.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.81 MAX_MED: 5.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: FD&C Green No. 3

CHID: 20673 CASRN: 2353-45-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N22

M4ID: 30008581

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	423.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.79 MAX_MED: 1.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexachloro-1,3-butadiene

CHID: 20683 CASRN: 87-68-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I18

M4ID: 30008705

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	513.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.03	MAX_MED:	4.08	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane

CHID: 20685 CASRN: 319-85-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H10

M4ID: 30008939

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	622.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.16 MAX_MED: 0.379 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexachlorocyclopentadiene

CHID: 20688 CASRN: 77-47-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F06

M4ID: 30008887

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	386.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.14 MAX_MED: 2.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methenamine

CHID: 20692 CASRN: 100-97-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G08

M4ID: 30008913

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	396.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.52 MAX_MED: 1.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 8-Hydroxyquinoline

CHID: 20730 CASRN: 148-24-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N06

M4ID: 30009079

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.275 MAX_MED: -0.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isophorone

CHID: 20759 CASRN: 78-59-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L05

M4ID: 30008646

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	506.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.11 MAX_MED: 4.91 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Maleic hydrazide

CHID: 20792 CASRN: 123-33-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C04

M4ID: 30008510

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.31 MAX_MED: 4.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: dL-Menthol

CHID: 20805 CASRN: 89-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I14

M4ID: 30008709

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	434.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.01 MAX_MED: 4.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl carbamate

CHID: 20834 CASRN: 598-55-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A22

M4ID: 30008545

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.24 MAX_MED: 7.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl methanesulfonate

CHID: 20845 CASRN: 66-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N15

M4ID: 30008364

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	423.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.56 MAX_MED: 1.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
 CHID: 20856 CASRN: 872-50-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A23
 M4ID: 30008487

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	548.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.32 MAX_MED: 6.13 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 6-Methylquinoline
 CHID: 20887 CASRN: 91-62-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C06
 M4ID: 30008456

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	520.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.52 MAX_MED: 4.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 6-Methyl-2-thiouracil
 CHID: 20890 CASRN: 56-04-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F19
 M4ID: 30008371

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.44 MAX_MED: 4.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Busulfan

CHID: 20910 CASRN: 55-98-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P15

M4ID: 30008792

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	488.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.68 MAX_MED: 3.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Naphthalene

CHID: 20913 CASRN: 91-20-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M02

M4ID: 30009051

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	389.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 2.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Naphthaleneacetic acid

CHID: 20915 CASRN: 86-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F05

M4ID: 30008886

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	382.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.68 MAX_MED: 2.28 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Naphthylamine

CHID: 20921 CASRN: 91-59-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G06

M4ID: 30008330

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	533.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.81 MAX_MED: 5.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nicotine

CHID: 20930 CASRN: 54-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D07

M4ID: 30008431

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	492.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.2 MAX_MED: 5.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nicotinic acid

CHID: 20932 CASRN: 59-67-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J10

M4ID: 30008689

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.36 MAX_MED: 1.45 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20943 CASRN: 99-59-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I11

M4ID: 30008712

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.05 MAX_MED: 5.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nitrofurazone

CHID: 20944 CASRN: 59-87-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078005

M4ID: 30008574

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.49 MAX_MED: 3.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Methyl-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20959 CASRN: 99-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G18

M4ID: 30008923

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.01 MAX_MED: 1.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nitrobenzene

CHID: 20964 CASRN: 98-95-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E23

M4ID: 30008880

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	379.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.27 MAX_MED: 2.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Nitrobenzoic acid

CHID: 20966 CASRN: 62-23-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I03

M4ID: 30008956

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	511.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.06 MAX_MED: 1.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nitrofen

CHID: 20970 CASRN: 1836-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N22

M4ID: 30008357

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	417.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.38 MAX_MED: 2.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodimethylamine

CHID: 21029 CASRN: 62-75-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P13

M4ID: 30008758

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	435.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.2 MAX_MED: 3.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodipropylamine
 CHID: 21032 CASRN: 621-64-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J14
 M4ID: 30008991

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	421.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.989 MAX_MED: 1.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Oxazepam

CHID: 21087 CASRN: 604-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A15

M4ID: 30008495

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.45 MAX_MED: 9.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Oxydianiline

CHID: 21094 CASRN: 101-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G10

M4ID: 30008326

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	515.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.72 MAX_MED: 6.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Oxytetracycline hydrochloride

CHID: 21097 CASRN: 2058-46-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P02

M4ID: 30008805

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	434.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.58 MAX_MED: 2.61 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phenylmercuric acetate

CHID: 21150 CASRN: 62-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E09

M4ID: 30008866

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.61 MAX_MED: 1.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Phenylphenol

CHID: 21151 CASRN: 90-43-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N03

M4ID: 30009076

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.77 MAX_MED: 2.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Prednisone

CHID: 21185 CASRN: 53-03-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I05

M4ID: 30008718

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.69 MAX_MED: 3.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propazine

CHID: 21196 CASRN: 139-40-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E18

M4ID: 30008875

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	554.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 21.3 MAX_MED: 4.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pebulate

CHID: 21199 CASRN: 1114-71-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H11

M4ID: 30008736

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.51 MAX_MED: 3.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 6-Propyl-2-thiouracil
 CHID: 21209 CASRN: 51-52-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A20
 M4ID: 30008490

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	644.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.77 MAX_MED: 8.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Retinol acetate

CHID: 21240 CASRN: 127-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G05

M4ID: 30008331

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	496.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.7 MAX_MED: 5.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Rifampicin

CHID: 21244 CASRN: 13292-46-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P17

M4ID: 30008790

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.9 MAX_MED: 4.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sulfasalazine

CHID: 21256 CASRN: 599-79-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M05

M4ID: 30008622

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.36 MAX_MED: 5.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium chlorite

CHID: 21272 CASRN: 7758-19-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J11

M4ID: 30008688

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	514.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.19 MAX_MED: 4.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2E,4E-Hexadienoic acid

CHID: 21277 CASRN: 110-44-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K24

M4ID: 30008651

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.48 MAX_MED: 4.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Disulfiram
 CHID: 21322 CASRN: 97-77-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G21
 M4ID: 30008750

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	559.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.59 MAX_MED: 9.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Thiourea

CHID: 21348 CASRN: 62-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L17

M4ID: 30009042

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	494.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.82 MAX_MED: 3.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: dl-alpha-Tocopheryl acetate
 CHID: 21356 CASRN: 52225-20-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D08
 M4ID: 30008430

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	578.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.12 MAX_MED: 6.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4,6-Trichlorophenol

CHID: 21386 CASRN: 88-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F06

M4ID: 30008384

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	549.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.76 MAX_MED: 6.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol

CHID: 21393 CASRN: 112-27-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078017

M4ID: 30008562

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.22 MAX_MED: 3.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Trifluralin
 CHID: 21395 CASRN: 1582-09-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B08
 M4ID: 30008530

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.95 MAX_MED: 3.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Trimethyl phosphate

CHID: 21403 CASRN: 512-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F18

M4ID: 30008899

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	475.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.2 MAX_MED: 5.28 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triphenyltin hydroxide

CHID: 21409 CASRN: 76-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I21

M4ID: 30008702

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	574.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.17 MAX_MED: -1.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Urethane
 CHID: 21427 CASRN: 51-79-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M11
 M4ID: 30009060

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.67 MAX_MED: 0.388 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: FD&C Yellow 5

CHID: 21455 CASRN: 1934-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C18

M4ID: 30008827

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.16 MAX_MED: 4.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ziram

CHID: 21464 CASRN: 137-30-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A08

M4ID: 30008502

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	622.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.76	MAX_MED:	5.54	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fumaric acid

CHID: 21518 CASRN: 110-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P23

M4ID: 30008768

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	502.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.6 MAX_MED: 5.75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21519 CASRN: 112-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N17

M4ID: 30008586

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	483.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.43 MAX_MED: 7.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 21520 CASRN: 143-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F16

M4ID: 30008374

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	556.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.27 MAX_MED: 5.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Decanal

CHID: 21553 CASRN: 112-31-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E24

M4ID: 30008390

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	469.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.79 MAX_MED: 3.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Decanoic acid

CHID: 21554 CASRN: 334-48-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D21

M4ID: 30008417

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	494.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.27 MAX_MED: 2.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dalapon

CHID: 21575 CASRN: 75-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P22

M4ID: 30008767

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	568.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.23 MAX_MED: 5.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Heptanoic acid

CHID: 21600 CASRN: 111-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P03

M4ID: 30008804

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	511.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.79 MAX_MED: 3.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexanoic acid

CHID: 21607 CASRN: 142-62-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N06

M4ID: 30008597

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	508.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.08 MAX_MED: 4.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nonanoic acid

CHID: 21641 CASRN: 112-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M21

M4ID: 30008606

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	425.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.58 MAX_MED: 1.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octadecanoic acid

CHID: 21642 CASRN: 57-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K07

M4ID: 30009008

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.51 MAX_MED: 2.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid

CHID: 21666 CASRN: 544-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L23

M4ID: 30008628

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	435.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.35 MAX_MED: 0.853 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Propanol

CHID: 21739 CASRN: 71-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N24

M4ID: 30008579

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.15 MAX_MED: 3.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5,5-Dimethylhydantoin
 CHID: 21754 CASRN: 77-71-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J07
 M4ID: 30008692

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	541.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.46 MAX_MED: 5.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate

CHID: 21758 CASRN: 78-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078022

M4ID: 30008557

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.22 MAX_MED: 4.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol

CHID: 21788 CASRN: 88-30-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091023

M4ID: 30008808

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	451.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.473 MAX_MED: 0.458 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Naphthol

CHID: 21793 CASRN: 90-15-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F01

M4ID: 30008882

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.35 MAX_MED: 2.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Quinoline

CHID: 21798 CASRN: 91-22-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I10

M4ID: 30008963

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	554.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.7 MAX_MED: 1.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N-Diethylaniline

CHID: 21800 CASRN: 91-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N02

M4ID: 30009075

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	394.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.47 MAX_MED: 2.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: o-Cresol

CHID: 21808 CASRN: 95-48-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N23

M4ID: 30008580

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.96 MAX_MED: 2.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloroaniline

CHID: 21815 CASRN: 95-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L22

M4ID: 30009047

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.4 MAX_MED: 3.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Butanone oxime

CHID: 21821 CASRN: 96-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H21

M4ID: 30008950

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	378.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 1.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acetophenone

CHID: 21828 CASRN: 98-86-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H08

M4ID: 30008739

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	540.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.04 MAX_MED: 5.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 21831 CASRN: 99-08-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B16

M4ID: 30008522

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.91 MAX_MED: 2.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N,4-Trimethylaniline

CHID: 21832 CASRN: 99-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078018

M4ID: 30008561

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.32 MAX_MED: 4.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanone oxime
 CHID: 21842 CASRN: 100-64-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M10
 M4ID: 30009059

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.373 MAX_MED: 1.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Ethyl-3-methylaniline

CHID: 21848 CASRN: 102-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N18

M4ID: 30008585

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	479.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.16 MAX_MED: 5.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethyl propanedioate

CHID: 21863 CASRN: 105-53-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F20

M4ID: 30008901

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	483.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.28 MAX_MED: 3.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 21864 CASRN: 105-67-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M08

M4ID: 30009057

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.93 MAX_MED: 1.61 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: p-Cresol

CHID: 21869 CASRN: 106-44-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A07

M4ID: 30008503

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.19 MAX_MED: 5.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Pentanone

CHID: 21888 CASRN: 107-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P12

M4ID: 30008795

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	639.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.97 MAX_MED: 2.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanol

CHID: 21894 CASRN: 108-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F17

M4ID: 30008373

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	418.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.08 MAX_MED: 3.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propanedinitrile

CHID: 21907 CASRN: 109-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F19

M4ID: 30008900

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	451.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.96 MAX_MED: 2.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5-Methyl-2-hexanone
 CHID: 21914 CASRN: 110-12-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K20
 M4ID: 30009021

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.35	MAX_MED:	3.57	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(Ethylamino)ethanol
 CHID: 21922 CASRN: 110-73-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G04
 M4ID: 30008332

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	514.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.42 MAX_MED: 5.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethylene glycol monoethyl ether acetate

CHID: 21928 CASRN: 111-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J20

M4ID: 30008679

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.94 MAX_MED: 5.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexanedinitrile

CHID: 21936 CASRN: 111-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M14

M4ID: 30009063

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.409 MAX_MED: -0.133 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Octanol

CHID: 21940 CASRN: 111-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F21

M4ID: 30008369

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	453.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.77 MAX_MED: 4.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21941 CASRN: 111-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G18

M4ID: 30008318

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	540.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.81 MAX_MED: 6.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Undecanone

CHID: 21943 CASRN: 112-12-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L07

M4ID: 30008644

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.64 MAX_MED: 4.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Decanol

CHID: 21946 CASRN: 112-30-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I22

M4ID: 30008701

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.76 MAX_MED: 1.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propoxur

CHID: 21948 CASRN: 114-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F08

M4ID: 30008889

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.09 MAX_MED: 1.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 21969 CASRN: 121-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M24

M4ID: 30008603

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	553.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.04 MAX_MED: 5.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethyl hexanoate

CHID: 21980 CASRN: 123-66-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M03

M4ID: 30008624

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05 MAX_MED: 1.92 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tributyl phosphate

CHID: 21986 CASRN: 126-73-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K01

M4ID: 30009002

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	418.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05 MAX_MED: 2.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: DEET

CHID: 21995 CASRN: 134-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A08

M4ID: 30008777

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	575.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.48 MAX_MED: 4.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethanolamine

CHID: 22000 CASRN: 141-43-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H21

M4ID: 30008726

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.43 MAX_MED: 2.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Nonanol

CHID: 22008 CASRN: 143-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M22

M4ID: 30008605

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	424.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.71 MAX_MED: 1.36 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Disulfoton
 CHID: 22018 CASRN: 298-04-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B23
 M4ID: 30008515

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	573.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.95 MAX_MED: 6.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bromacil

CHID: 22020 CASRN: 314-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G10

M4ID: 30008915

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	526.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.364 MAX_MED: 0.596 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dichlorobenzene
 CHID: 22056 CASRN: 541-73-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C22
 M4ID: 30008831

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.46 MAX_MED: 2.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propanil

CHID: 22111 CASRN: 709-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N24

M4ID: 30008355

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.26 MAX_MED: 1.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloro-1-butene
 CHID: 22113 CASRN: 760-23-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H24
 M4ID: 30008723

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	425.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.19 MAX_MED: 3.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: (Z)-3-Hexen-1-ol

CHID: 22137 CASRN: 928-96-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M18

M4ID: 30008609

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.23 MAX_MED: 4.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bromoxynil

CHID: 22162 CASRN: 1689-84-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E21

M4ID: 30008878

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.8 MAX_MED: 1.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: EPN

CHID: 22174 CASRN: 2104-64-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078010

M4ID: 30008569

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.56 MAX_MED: 5.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,3,6-Trimethylphenol

CHID: 22187 CASRN: 2416-94-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G11

M4ID: 30008325

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	485.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.64 MAX_MED: 3.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(Butan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 22331 CASRN: 89-72-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K15

M4ID: 30009016

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	453.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.93 MAX_MED: 2.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phenol red

CHID: 22408 CASRN: 143-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A06

M4ID: 30008775

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	512.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.91 MAX_MED: 3.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Methylenebis(2,6-di-t-butylphenol)

CHID: 22411 CASRN: 118-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I02

M4ID: 30008721

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	544.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.3 MAX_MED: 0.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Melatonin

CHID: 22421 CASRN: 73-31-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E07

M4ID: 30008407

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	475.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.85 MAX_MED: 3.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butylbenzene

CHID: 22472 CASRN: 104-51-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C21

M4ID: 30008830

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	395.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.54 MAX_MED: 2.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Corticosterone

CHID: 22474 CASRN: 50-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091005

M4ID: 30008350

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	512.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.24 MAX_MED: 5.36 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: E-Cinnamic acid

CHID: 22489 CASRN: 140-10-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B01

M4ID: 30008485

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	671.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.45 MAX_MED: 5.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Digoxin

CHID: 22934 CASRN: 20830-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F14

M4ID: 30008376

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	629.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.31 MAX_MED: 5.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Lactose

CHID: 23193 CASRN: 63-42-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M01

M4ID: 30008626

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	628.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.888 MAX_MED: 0.706 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Letrozole

CHID: 23202 CASRN: 112809-51-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K22

M4ID: 30009023

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	436.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.81 MAX_MED: 3.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Mifepristone

CHID: 23322 CASRN: 84371-65-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B01

M4ID: 30008548

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.73 MAX_MED: 5.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol tetranitrate

CHID: 23430 CASRN: 78-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F02

M4ID: 30008883

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.67 MAX_MED: 9.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyridoxine

CHID: 23541 CASRN: 65-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G01

M4ID: 30008906

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	376.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.77 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Retinol

CHID: 23556 CASRN: 68-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H14

M4ID: 30008733

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	459.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.38 MAX_MED: 3.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butanedioic acid

CHID: 23602 CASRN: 110-15-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I07

M4ID: 30008960

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.46 MAX_MED: 1.44 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tetracycline

CHID: 23645 CASRN: 60-54-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C11

M4ID: 30008451

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	493.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.15 MAX_MED: 5.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 6-Thioguanine

CHID: 23652 CASRN: 154-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E05

M4ID: 30008409

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.39 MAX_MED: 3.13 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Warfarin

CHID: 23742 CASRN: 81-81-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B07

M4ID: 30008479

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.82 MAX_MED: 4.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: D-Xylose

CHID: 23745 CASRN: 58-86-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J12

M4ID: 30008989

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.77 MAX_MED: 3.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 23792 CASRN: 99-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D06

M4ID: 30008432

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.29 MAX_MED: 6.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isophorone diisocyanate
 CHID: 23826 CASRN: 4098-71-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B08
 M4ID: 30008478

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	563.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.32 MAX_MED: 6.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acenaphthylene

CHID: 23845 CASRN: 208-96-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A06

M4ID: 30008504

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	658.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	9.84	MAX_MED:	9.71	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acephate

CHID: 23846 CASRN: 30560-19-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C19

M4ID: 30008443

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	533.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.02 MAX_MED: 5.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acetochlor
CHID: 23848 CASRN: 34256-82-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E24
M4ID: 30008881

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.48 MAX_MED: 1.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Aldoxycarb

CHID: 23862 CASRN: 1646-88-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078001

M4ID: 30008578

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	629.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.35 MAX_MED: 1.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Amitraz

CHID: 23871 CASRN: 33089-61-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D08

M4ID: 30008841

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.1 MAX_MED: 1.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Anisidine

CHID: 23877 CASRN: 90-04-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I10

M4ID: 30008713

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.69 MAX_MED: 1.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Clofentezine

CHID: 23881 CASRN: 74115-24-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M05

M4ID: 30009054

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	448.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.425 MAX_MED: 0.124 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Asulam

CHID: 23890 CASRN: 3337-71-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F10

M4ID: 30008380

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.73 MAX_MED: 2.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benfluralin

CHID: 23899 CASRN: 1861-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L04

M4ID: 30009029

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.73 MAX_MED: 4.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bentazone

CHID: 23901 CASRN: 25057-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F04

M4ID: 30008885

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.18 MAX_MED: 3.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzo(b)fluoranthene

CHID: 23907 CASRN: 205-99-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I23

M4ID: 30008976

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	333.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.43 MAX_MED: 4.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butylate

CHID: 23936 CASRN: 2008-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B05

M4ID: 30008533

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.79 MAX_MED: 3.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Carbosulfan

CHID: 23950 CASRN: 55285-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A15

M4ID: 30008538

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	570.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.52 MAX_MED: 7.45 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Carboxin

CHID: 23951 CASRN: 5234-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C16

M4ID: 30008825

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.65 MAX_MED: 2.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexylamine

CHID: 23996 CASRN: 108-91-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F08

M4ID: 30008382

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	558.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.77 MAX_MED: 9.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cypermethrin

CHID: 23998 CASRN: 52315-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N09

M4ID: 30008594

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	591.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.36 MAX_MED: 2.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyromazine

CHID: 23999 CASRN: 66215-27-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091007

M4ID: 30008348

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	457.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1 MAX_MED: 1.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dicamba

CHID: 24018 CASRN: 1918-00-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A10

M4ID: 30008779

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	588.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.49 MAX_MED: 6.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethyl sulfate

CHID: 24045 CASRN: 64-67-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M20

M4ID: 30008607

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.19 MAX_MED: 6.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diisopropyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 24051 CASRN: 1445-75-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091015

M4ID: 30008340

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	431.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.41 MAX_MED: 1.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethipin

CHID: 24052 CASRN: 55290-64-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K13

M4ID: 30008662

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2 MAX_MED: 2.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfite

CHID: 24055 CASRN: 77-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D03

M4ID: 30008836

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	377.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.32 MAX_MED: 2.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethylamine

CHID: 24057 CASRN: 124-40-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J05

M4ID: 30008982

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.331 MAX_MED: 0.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine
 CHID: 24059 CASRN: 119-93-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G09
 M4ID: 30008914

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	582.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.812 MAX_MED: 0.989 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24062 CASRN: 95-65-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E15

M4ID: 30008872

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.08 MAX_MED: 1.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24063 CASRN: 576-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A19

M4ID: 30008491

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	599.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.11 MAX_MED: 6.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dinitrobenzene

CHID: 24065 CASRN: 99-65-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N14

M4ID: 30008365

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.355 MAX_MED: 0.396 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diphenamid

CHID: 24072 CASRN: 957-51-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B12

M4ID: 30008526

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	415.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.54 MAX_MED: 3.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethion

CHID: 24086 CASRN: 563-12-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E19

M4ID: 30008395

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	588.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.58 MAX_MED: 4.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Butoxyethanol

CHID: 24097 CASRN: 111-76-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M12

M4ID: 30008615

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.7 MAX_MED: 5.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fenamiphos

CHID: 24102 CASRN: 22224-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C08

M4ID: 30008817

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	442.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.15 MAX_MED: 3.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Flutolanil

CHID: 24109 CASRN: 66332-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G17

M4ID: 30008922

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.32 MAX_MED: 1.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fomesafen

CHID: 24112 CASRN: 72178-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A16

M4ID: 30008539

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.62 MAX_MED: 4.42 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isopropalin

CHID: 24157 CASRN: 33820-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N12

M4ID: 30008591

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.96 MAX_MED: 6.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Lactofen

CHID: 24160 CASRN: 77501-63-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I01

M4ID: 30008954

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.82 MAX_MED: 5.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methacrylonitrile

CHID: 24176 CASRN: 126-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C20

M4ID: 30008829

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	497.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.65 MAX_MED: 4.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methamidophos

CHID: 24177 CASRN: 10265-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A04

M4ID: 30008773

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.93	MAX_MED:	6.65	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: MCPB

CHID: 24193 CASRN: 94-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K13

M4ID: 30009014

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.37 MAX_MED: 1.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Mecoprop

CHID: 24194 CASRN: 93-65-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P03

M4ID: 30008552

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	507.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.97 MAX_MED: 6.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: m-Cresol

CHID: 24200 CASRN: 108-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I19

M4ID: 30008972

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.56 MAX_MED: 3.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nitrapyrin

CHID: 24216 CASRN: 1929-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G04

M4ID: 30008909

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	439.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.84 MAX_MED: 1.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Oxyfluorfen
 CHID: 24241 CASRN: 42874-03-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L08
 M4ID: 30009033

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	500.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.25 MAX_MED: 1.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phosphoric acid

CHID: 24263 CASRN: 7664-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K14

M4ID: 30009015

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	480.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.19	MAX_MED: 3.22	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Prometryn

CHID: 24272 CASRN: 7287-19-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G16

M4ID: 30008921

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.42 MAX_MED: 0.162 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propargite
 CHID: 24276 CASRN: 2312-35-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D06
 M4ID: 30008839

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.41 MAX_MED: 2.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyrene
 CHID: 24289 CASRN: 129-00-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M23
 M4ID: 30009072

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	416.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.47 MAX_MED: 1.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexythiazox

CHID: 24299 CASRN: 78587-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I24

M4ID: 30008977

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	400.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.16 MAX_MED: 2.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sethoxydim

CHID: 24304 CASRN: 74051-80-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D09

M4ID: 30008842

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.93 MAX_MED: 2.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium fluoroacetate

CHID: 24311 CASRN: 62-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N13

M4ID: 30008590

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.86 MAX_MED: -1.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Myclobutanil

CHID: 24315 CASRN: 88671-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G24

M4ID: 30008747

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	499.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.45 MAX_MED: 4.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tebuthiuron

CHID: 24316 CASRN: 34014-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M04

M4ID: 30009053

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	456.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.939 MAX_MED: 0.727 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2,4,5-Tetrachlorobenzene

CHID: 24320 CASRN: 95-94-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C24

M4ID: 30008833

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.38 MAX_MED: 3.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Thiophanate-methyl

CHID: 24338 CASRN: 23564-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I19

M4ID: 30008704

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.91 MAX_MED: 4.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tri-allate

CHID: 24344 CASRN: 2303-17-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K16

M4ID: 30009017

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.47 MAX_MED: 1.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4,5-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 24359 CASRN: 95-95-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J22
 M4ID: 30008999

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.16 MAX_MED: 2.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 24368 CASRN: 112-50-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J02

M4ID: 30008979

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.69 MAX_MED: 8.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acetic acid

CHID: 24394 CASRN: 64-19-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078023

M4ID: 30008556

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.5 MAX_MED: 2.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Aminobenzoic acid

CHID: 24466 CASRN: 150-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C13

M4ID: 30008449

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.03 MAX_MED: 6.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5-Amino-2-methylphenol

CHID: 24489 CASRN: 2835-95-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N10

M4ID: 30008593

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	578.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0986 MAX_MED: -0.201 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 24621 CASRN: 111-96-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G03

M4ID: 30008333

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.02 MAX_MED: 0.983 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-propanol

CHID: 24657 CASRN: 627-18-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E05

M4ID: 30008862

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	348.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.784 MAX_MED: 0.789 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylamine

CHID: 24681 CASRN: 75-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P18

M4ID: 30008789

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	551.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.76 MAX_MED: 7.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: D-Camphor

CHID: 24721 CASRN: 464-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G14

M4ID: 30008322

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	496.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.7 MAX_MED: 3.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Carbendazim

CHID: 24729 CASRN: 10605-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P06

M4ID: 30008801

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4 MAX_MED: 4.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Colchicine

CHID: 24845 CASRN: 64-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J06

M4ID: 30008983

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	562.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.13 MAX_MED: -0.279 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cycloheximide

CHID: 24882 CASRN: 66-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D09

M4ID: 30008429

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	609.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.4	MAX_MED:	1.92	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,6-Hexanediamine

CHID: 24922 CASRN: 124-09-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L20

M4ID: 30009045

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	474.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 2.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Diaminotoluene

CHID: 24930 CASRN: 496-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M03

M4ID: 30009052

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	508.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.82 MAX_MED: 1.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Di-tert-butyl peroxide

CHID: 24955 CASRN: 110-05-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F23

M4ID: 30008904

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	361.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.44 MAX_MED: 1.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Dichlorodiphenyl sulfone

CHID: 24986 CASRN: 80-07-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B22

M4ID: 30008516

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.01 MAX_MED: 3.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzal chloride

CHID: 25014 CASRN: 98-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D05

M4ID: 30008838

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	376.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.85 MAX_MED: 2.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 25049 CASRN: 111-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I24

M4ID: 30008699

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	412.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.88 MAX_MED: 2.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethylenetriamine

CHID: 25050 CASRN: 111-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N03

M4ID: 30008600

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	453.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.93 MAX_MED: 2.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dihexyl phthalate

CHID: 25068 CASRN: 84-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H12

M4ID: 30008735

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	605.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.48 MAX_MED: 8.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diisobutyl ketone

CHID: 25080 CASRN: 108-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D12

M4ID: 30008426

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.81	MAX_MED:	5.21	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl adipate

CHID: 25096 CASRN: 627-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K16

M4ID: 30008659

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	595.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.43 MAX_MED: 6.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-(Dimethylamino)propylamine

CHID: 25102 CASRN: 109-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K01

M4ID: 30008674

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	701.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.62 MAX_MED: 9.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl glutarate

CHID: 25122 CASRN: 1119-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J22

M4ID: 30008677

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	415.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.59 MAX_MED: 2.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene

CHID: 25132 CASRN: 83-41-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L01

M4ID: 30009026

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	384.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 1.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dimethylolurea
 CHID: 25141 CASRN: 140-95-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M12
 M4ID: 30009061

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	567.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.82 MAX_MED: 1.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Divinylbenzene

CHID: 25216 CASRN: 1321-74-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K04

M4ID: 30008671

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	471.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.55 MAX_MED: 2.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: (2-Dodecenyl)succinic anhydride

CHID: 25217 CASRN: 19780-11-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J02

M4ID: 30008697

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.19 MAX_MED: 2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexanoic acid

CHID: 25293 CASRN: 149-57-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L12

M4ID: 30008639

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	533.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.08 MAX_MED: 5.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate

CHID: 25300 CASRN: 1241-94-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G17

M4ID: 30008319

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	544.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.3 MAX_MED: 4.36 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5-Ethylidene-2-norbornene

CHID: 25306 CASRN: 16219-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H22

M4ID: 30008951

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	423.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.27 MAX_MED: 3.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Formamide

CHID: 25337 CASRN: 75-12-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K20

M4ID: 30008655

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.38 MAX_MED: 6.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexamethyldisilazane

CHID: 25395 CASRN: 999-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N23

M4ID: 30008356

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	380.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.06 MAX_MED: 1.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxy-2-methylpropanenitrile

CHID: 25427 CASRN: 75-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G20

M4ID: 30008925

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.68 MAX_MED: 2.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hydroxyurea

CHID: 25438 CASRN: 127-07-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F24

M4ID: 30008905

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	378.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.11 MAX_MED: 2.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Methylbutyl acetate

CHID: 25453 CASRN: 123-92-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M17

M4ID: 30008610

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	434.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.18 MAX_MED: 3.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isopentyl alcohol

CHID: 25469 CASRN: 123-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N19

M4ID: 30008584

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 3.69 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl acetate

CHID: 25478 CASRN: 108-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P20

M4ID: 30008765

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	609.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.42 MAX_MED: 7.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isoproterenol hydrochloride

CHID: 25486 CASRN: 51-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H10

M4ID: 30008737

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	505.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.3 MAX_MED: 0.988 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Linalool

CHID: 25502 CASRN: 78-70-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G23

M4ID: 30008748

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	396.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.71 MAX_MED: 1.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Linoleic acid

CHID: 25505 CASRN: 60-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C08

M4ID: 30008454

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	614.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.72 MAX_MED: 7.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl 2-aminobenzoate
 CHID: 25567 CASRN: 134-20-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H04
 M4ID: 30008933

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	480.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.1 MAX_MED: 0.813 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide

CHID: 25595 CASRN: 110-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I15

M4ID: 30008968

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.15 MAX_MED: 4.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methylene bis(thiocyanate)

CHID: 25599 CASRN: 6317-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M19

M4ID: 30008608

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	491.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.94 MAX_MED: 2.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Myrcene

CHID: 25692 CASRN: 123-35-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E16

M4ID: 30008873

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	296.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.44 MAX_MED: 1.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,10-Phenanthroline

CHID: 25857 CASRN: 66-71-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H18

M4ID: 30008947

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	514.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.28 MAX_MED: 2.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Ethoxyaniline

CHID: 25864 CASRN: 156-43-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A09

M4ID: 30008778

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	602.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.24 MAX_MED: 8.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethyl 3-phenylglycidate

CHID: 25886 CASRN: 121-39-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D01

M4ID: 30008437

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	651.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.71 MAX_MED: 2.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Phenyl-1,4-benzenediamine

CHID: 25895 CASRN: 101-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I08

M4ID: 30008715

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.31 MAX_MED: 5.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium dodecyl sulfate

CHID: 26031 CASRN: 151-21-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H22

M4ID: 30008725

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	492.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.28 MAX_MED: 3.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Terephthalic acid

CHID: 26080 CASRN: 100-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B14

M4ID: 30008472

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.28 MAX_MED: 5.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride

CHID: 26102 CASRN: 117-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I03

M4ID: 30008720

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	474.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.49 MAX_MED: 1.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Theobromine

CHID: 26132 CASRN: 83-67-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P14

M4ID: 30008759

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.19 MAX_MED: 2.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tolyltriazole

CHID: 26171 CASRN: 29385-43-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N11

M4ID: 30008592

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	513.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.69 MAX_MED: 4.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triclocarban

CHID: 26214 CASRN: 101-20-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L21

M4ID: 30009046

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.84 MAX_MED: 2.75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 26224 CASRN: 112-49-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M01

M4ID: 30009050

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	365.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.984 MAX_MED: 1.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Trimellitic anhydride

CHID: 26235 CASRN: 552-30-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G16

M4ID: 30008320

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	553.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.09 MAX_MED: 6.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triglycidyl isocyanurate

CHID: 26262 CASRN: 2451-62-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I06

M4ID: 30008959

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	430.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2 MAX_MED: 2.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Camphene

CHID: 26488 CASRN: 79-92-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C23

M4ID: 30008439

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	407.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.01 MAX_MED: 3.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide

CHID: 26513 CASRN: 85-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M16

M4ID: 30008611

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.12 MAX_MED: 5.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phthalimide

CHID: 26514 CASRN: 85-41-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P08

M4ID: 30008799

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.15 MAX_MED: 3.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Symclosene

CHID: 26523 CASRN: 87-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I04

M4ID: 30008957

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.25 MAX_MED: 2.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Tert-Butyl-5-methylphenol

CHID: 26529 CASRN: 88-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C05

M4ID: 30008814

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	413.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.42 MAX_MED: 1.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol bis(2-ethylhexanoate)

CHID: 26564 CASRN: 94-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F03

M4ID: 30008884

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	541.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.99 MAX_MED: 5.91 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylcyclohexanol

CHID: 26623 CASRN: 98-52-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B13

M4ID: 30008525

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.79 MAX_MED: 3.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Diisopropylbenzene

CHID: 26640 CASRN: 99-62-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P19

M4ID: 30008764

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	557.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7 MAX_MED: 6.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenedicarbonyl dichloride

CHID: 26641 CASRN: 99-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P07

M4ID: 30008800

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.85 MAX_MED: 2.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: p-Cymene

CHID: 26645 CASRN: 99-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L09

M4ID: 30009034

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.39 MAX_MED: 1.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid

CHID: 26647 CASRN: 99-96-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L14

M4ID: 30008637

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	378.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.05 MAX_MED: 1.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Pyridinecarbonitrile
 CHID: 26665 CASRN: 100-54-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B18
 M4ID: 30008520

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	494.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.4 MAX_MED: 4.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)octanal

CHID: 26684 CASRN: 101-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J16

M4ID: 30008683

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	628.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	9.59	MAX_MED:	9.73	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triacetin

CHID: 26691 CASRN: 102-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K22

M4ID: 30008653

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.65 MAX_MED: 3.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl acetate

CHID: 26694 CASRN: 103-09-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D03

M4ID: 30008435

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	530.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.04 MAX_MED: 5.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-pentanol
 CHID: 26781 CASRN: 108-11-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H19
 M4ID: 30008728

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.59 MAX_MED: 4.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Methylaniline

CHID: 26792 CASRN: 108-44-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L18

M4ID: 30008633

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	491.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.17 MAX_MED: 4.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzenethiol

CHID: 26811 CASRN: 108-98-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M04

M4ID: 30008623

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.6 MAX_MED: 2.92 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl tetradecanoate

CHID: 26838 CASRN: 110-27-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B06

M4ID: 30008480

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	589.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.13 MAX_MED: 7.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl decanoate

CHID: 26842 CASRN: 110-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P21

M4ID: 30008786

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.32 MAX_MED: 4.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl octanoate

CHID: 26864 CASRN: 111-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J21

M4ID: 30008998

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.98 MAX_MED: 2.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexamethyleneimine

CHID: 26879 CASRN: 111-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M19

M4ID: 30009068

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.11 MAX_MED: 2.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Ethanedioyl diacetate

CHID: 26880 CASRN: 111-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N18

M4ID: 30008361

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	466.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.14 MAX_MED: 2.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 26912 CASRN: 112-35-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H17

M4ID: 30008730

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.87 MAX_MED: 3.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Undecanol

CHID: 26915 CASRN: 112-42-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G15

M4ID: 30008920

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	438.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.14 MAX_MED: 2.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tetraethylene glycol

CHID: 26922 CASRN: 112-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E17

M4ID: 30008397

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.5 MAX_MED: 8.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol

CHID: 26943 CASRN: 115-77-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M13

M4ID: 30008614

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	412.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.334 MAX_MED: -0.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 26997 CASRN: 123-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B23

M4ID: 30008463

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	454.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.47 MAX_MED: 3.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate

CHID: 27050 CASRN: 128-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P10

M4ID: 30008755

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.42 MAX_MED: 2.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium phenolate

CHID: 27072 CASRN: 139-02-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F07

M4ID: 30008888

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	387.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.66 MAX_MED: 2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bis(2-ethylhexyl) maleate

CHID: 27094 CASRN: 142-16-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L03

M4ID: 30008648

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.12 MAX_MED: 4.75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1H-1,2,4-Triazole

CHID: 27131 CASRN: 288-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078015

M4ID: 30008564

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	500.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.48 MAX_MED: 4.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Cyclopentadiene
 CHID: 27191 CASRN: 542-92-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J20
 M4ID: 30008997

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.93 MAX_MED: 3.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl isothiocyanate
 CHID: 27204 CASRN: 556-61-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G24
 M4ID: 30008929

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	384.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.27 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane

CHID: 27205 CASRN: 556-67-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G14

M4ID: 30008919

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.461 MAX_MED: 0.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Diethylaniline

CHID: 27218 CASRN: 579-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091001

M4ID: 30008354

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	431.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0209 MAX_MED: 0.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Pyrrolidinone

CHID: 27246 CASRN: 616-45-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H19

M4ID: 30008948

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 2.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl formate

CHID: 27258 CASRN: 625-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F03

M4ID: 30008387

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.72 MAX_MED: 4.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pentyl acetate

CHID: 27263 CASRN: 628-63-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J23

M4ID: 30008676

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	414.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.67 MAX_MED: 1.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phenyl phosphorus dichloride

CHID: 27282 CASRN: 644-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D20

M4ID: 30008853

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.53 MAX_MED: 4.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dibutyltin dichloride

CHID: 27292 CASRN: 683-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H06

M4ID: 30008935

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	629.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.59 MAX_MED: -0.256 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Phenoxy-2-propanol
 CHID: 27312 CASRN: 770-35-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H20
 M4ID: 30008949

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.96 MAX_MED: 2.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ammonium carbamate

CHID: 27360 CASRN: 1111-78-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N05

M4ID: 30008598

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.09 MAX_MED: 4.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diisooctyl adipate

CHID: 27388 CASRN: 1330-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A13

M4ID: 30008497

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	594.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.84 MAX_MED: 7.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phenolsulfonic acid

CHID: 27390 CASRN: 1333-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B07

M4ID: 30008531

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.14 MAX_MED: 3.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylacetoacetamide

CHID: 27454 CASRN: 2044-64-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L05

M4ID: 30009030

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.531 MAX_MED: -0.397 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Thiocarbazine

CHID: 27461 CASRN: 2231-57-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I20

M4ID: 30008973

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.09 MAX_MED: 2.45 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol

CHID: 27479 CASRN: 2440-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F15

M4ID: 30008375

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	586.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.53 MAX_MED: 7.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,3-Diaminotoluene

CHID: 27494 CASRN: 2687-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M10

M4ID: 30008617

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.753 MAX_MED: 0.107 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-D sodium salt

CHID: 27496 CASRN: 2702-72-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H18

M4ID: 30008729

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	499.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.69 MAX_MED: 4.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Potassium 2-ethylhexanoate

CHID: 27525 CASRN: 3164-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G19

M4ID: 30008924

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.81 MAX_MED: 3.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium chloroacetate

CHID: 27550 CASRN: 3926-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091020

M4ID: 30008335

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.62 MAX_MED: 2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Chlorobenzotrifluoride

CHID: 27593 CASRN: 5216-25-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P01

M4ID: 30008806

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	425.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.77 MAX_MED: 2.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzenemethanol

CHID: 27756 CASRN: 13826-35-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L22

M4ID: 30008629

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	619.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.8 MAX_MED: 7.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid

CHID: 27770 CASRN: 15214-89-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L18

M4ID: 30009043

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	466.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.02 MAX_MED: 2.69 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dicyclohexyl sodium sulfosuccinate

CHID: 27826 CASRN: 23386-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M16

M4ID: 30009065

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	499.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.651 MAX_MED: 1.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: tert-Nonanethiol

CHID: 27868 CASRN: 25360-10-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K23

M4ID: 30009024

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	283.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.33 MAX_MED: 4.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Calcium dodecylbenzene sulfonate

CHID: 27891 CASRN: 26264-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G13

M4ID: 30008918

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.56 MAX_MED: -1.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ammonium xylene sulfonate

CHID: 27899 CASRN: 26447-10-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C04

M4ID: 30008458

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	610.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.58	MAX_MED:	5.51	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Neodecanoic acid

CHID: 27916 CASRN: 26896-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H07

M4ID: 30008936

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.98 MAX_MED: 1.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diisodecyl hexanedioate

CHID: 27924 CASRN: 27178-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B24

M4ID: 30008514

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	548.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.64 MAX_MED: 2.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dodecylbenzene sulfonate triethanolamine(1:1)

CHID: 27932 CASRN: 27323-41-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C01

M4ID: 30008513

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	488.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.43 MAX_MED: 4.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 27983 CASRN: 34590-94-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F23

M4ID: 30008811

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	353.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.19 MAX_MED: 1.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Hexadecanol

CHID: 27991 CASRN: 36653-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H08

M4ID: 30008937

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	310.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.55 MAX_MED: 5.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dichlormid

CHID: 27997 CASRN: 37764-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D11

M4ID: 30008427

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	471.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.27 MAX_MED: 5.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: DINP branched

CHID: 28665 CASRN: 68515-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H03

M4ID: 30008744

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	296.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.77 MAX_MED: 4.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol

CHID: 29128 CASRN: 97-99-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078004

M4ID: 30008575

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	480.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.47 MAX_MED: 3.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyclopentanone

CHID: 29154 CASRN: 120-92-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I04

M4ID: 30008719

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	485.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.6 MAX_MED: 4.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)-heptanal

CHID: 29157 CASRN: 122-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J24

M4ID: 30008675

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.62 MAX_MED: 4.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,6,8-Trimethyl-4-nonanol

CHID: 29159 CASRN: 123-17-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J15

M4ID: 30008684

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.61 MAX_MED: 6.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 29162 CASRN: 126-06-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E07

M4ID: 30008864

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	414.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.31 MAX_MED: 2.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one

CHID: 29170 CASRN: 141-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A03

M4ID: 30008507

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	603	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.69 MAX_MED: 7.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methylionone

CHID: 29214 CASRN: 1335-46-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P17

M4ID: 30008762

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.62 MAX_MED: 9.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Clopyralid

CHID: 29221 CASRN: 1702-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D04

M4ID: 30008837

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.6 MAX_MED: 5.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol

CHID: 29241 CASRN: 2772-45-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J04

M4ID: 30008981

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	587.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.68 MAX_MED: 2.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triethoxyoctylsilane

CHID: 29246 CASRN: 2943-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091008

M4ID: 30008347

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 1.69 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium lauryl polyoxyethylene ether sulfate

CHID: 29298 CASRN: 9004-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J21

M4ID: 30008678

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	546.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.35	MAX_MED:	5.37	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl stearate
 CHID: 29304 CASRN: 11099-07-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D02
 M4ID: 30008436

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	602.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.08 MAX_MED: 8.64 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tripropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 29329 CASRN: 25498-49-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K04

M4ID: 30009005

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.65 MAX_MED: 2.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diazolidinyl urea

CHID: 29559 CASRN: 78491-02-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J18

M4ID: 30008995

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.5 MAX_MED: 3.44 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methacrylamide

CHID: 29600 CASRN: 79-39-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J19

M4ID: 30008680

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.02 MAX_MED: 5.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Limonene

CHID: 29612 CASRN: 138-86-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I23

M4ID: 30008700

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05 MAX_MED: 2.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Thiocyanic acid, ammonium salt

CHID: 29653 CASRN: 1762-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M24

M4ID: 30009073

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.46 MAX_MED: 1.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 29661 CASRN: 3452-97-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C23

M4ID: 30008832

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.83 MAX_MED: 3.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Silica

CHID: 29677 CASRN: 7631-86-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J17

M4ID: 30008682

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.19 MAX_MED: 9.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium persulfate

CHID: 29698 CASRN: 7775-27-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M07

M4ID: 30009056

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.25 MAX_MED: 0.883 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Propanediol monobutyl ether
 CHID: 29755 CASRN: 29387-86-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I15
 M4ID: 30008708 BRK

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	615.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	101.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 189 MAX_MED: 7.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fenofibrate

CHID: 29874 CASRN: 49562-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H05

M4ID: 30008742

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.4 MAX_MED: 8.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Glycoluril

CHID: 31380 CASRN: 496-46-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G02

M4ID: 30008334

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	616.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.31 MAX_MED: 3.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Perfluorononanoic acid
 CHID: 31863 CASRN: 375-95-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C02
 M4ID: 30008512

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.8 MAX_MED: 4.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Perfluorooctanoic acid
CHID: 31865 CASRN: 335-67-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G02
M4ID: 30008907

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	430.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.5 MAX_MED: 3.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Chlorhexidine diacetate

CHID: 32345 CASRN: 56-95-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J10

M4ID: 30008987

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	632.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.72	MAX_MED:	2.04	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dichlobenil

CHID: 32365 CASRN: 1194-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L21

M4ID: 30008630

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.33 MAX_MED: 2.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethenamid

CHID: 32376 CASRN: 87674-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G23

M4ID: 30008928

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	310.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.33 MAX_MED: 3.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethalfluralin

CHID: 32386 CASRN: 55283-68-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M22

M4ID: 30009071

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.42 MAX_MED: 4.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Formetanate hydrochloride

CHID: 32405 CASRN: 23422-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I16

M4ID: 30008969

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.49 MAX_MED: 4.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Profenofos

CHID: 32464 CASRN: 41198-08-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K05

M4ID: 30009006

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	426.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.33 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triclopyr

CHID: 32497 CASRN: 55335-06-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E06

M4ID: 30008408

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.77 MAX_MED: 6.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxyethyl octyl sulfide

CHID: 32516 CASRN: 3547-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F16

M4ID: 30008897

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	479.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.63 MAX_MED: 3.69 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4,5-Dichloro-3H-1,2-dithiol-3-one

CHID: 32518 CASRN: 1192-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F24

M4ID: 30008812

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3 MAX_MED: 3.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acibenzolar-S-methyl

CHID: 32519 CASRN: 135158-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A11

M4ID: 30008499

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.73 MAX_MED: 8.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Benzisothiazolin-3-one

CHID: 32523 CASRN: 2634-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E22

M4ID: 30008392

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.7 MAX_MED: 3.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bifenazate

CHID: 32525 CASRN: 149877-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G22

M4ID: 30008927

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.41 MAX_MED: 1.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Etridiazole

CHID: 32547 CASRN: 2593-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E08

M4ID: 30008865

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.15 MAX_MED: 2.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fenpyroximate (Z,E)
 CHID: 32550 CASRN: 111812-58-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E11
 M4ID: 30008868

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	615.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.52 MAX_MED: 0.833 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluazinam
 CHID: 32551 CASRN: 79622-59-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A01
 M4ID: 30008770

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	573.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.11 MAX_MED: 6.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Prallethrin

CHID: 32572 CASRN: 23031-36-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078019

M4ID: 30008560

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	525.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.21 MAX_MED: 4.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyridaben

CHID: 32573 CASRN: 96489-71-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M09

M4ID: 30009058

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	623.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.881 MAX_MED: 0.682 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tefluthrin
 CHID: 32577 CASRN: 79538-32-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078013
 M4ID: 30008566

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.83	MAX_MED: 2.77	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyproconazole

CHID: 32601 CASRN: 94361-06-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J03

M4ID: 30008696

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.67 MAX_MED: 3.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fenitrothion

CHID: 32613 CASRN: 122-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091018

M4ID: 30008337

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.49 MAX_MED: 7.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Flumetsulam

CHID: 32615 CASRN: 98967-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078016

M4ID: 30008563

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	592.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.79 MAX_MED: 6.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pymetrozine

CHID: 32637 CASRN: 123312-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I20

M4ID: 30008703

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.52 MAX_MED: 4.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyraclostrobin

CHID: 32638 CASRN: 175013-18-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L24

M4ID: 30009049

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.04 MAX_MED: 1.13 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyridate
 CHID: 32639 CASRN: 55512-33-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E13
 M4ID: 30008870

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.992 MAX_MED: 1.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamide

CHID: 32646 CASRN: 4151-50-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D04

M4ID: 30008434

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	621.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.4 MAX_MED: 9.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(Thiocyanomethylthio)benzothiazole

CHID: 32647 CASRN: 21564-17-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K10

M4ID: 30009011

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	541.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 2.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Z-Tetrachlorvinphos

CHID: 32648 CASRN: 22248-79-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N21

M4ID: 30008358

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.95 MAX_MED: 1.92 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tetramethrin

CHID: 32649 CASRN: 7696-12-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091004

M4ID: 30008351

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	522.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.73 MAX_MED: 4.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Indoxacarb

CHID: 32690 CASRN: 173584-44-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H09

M4ID: 30008738

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	251.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2 MAX_MED: 2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Aldicarb sulfoxide

CHID: 33161 CASRN: 1646-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E16

M4ID: 30008398

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.64 MAX_MED: 7.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyclopentanol

CHID: 33371 CASRN: 96-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A05

M4ID: 30008505

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	569.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	8.37	MAX_MED:	8.03	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tebufenpyrad

CHID: 34223 CASRN: 119168-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G06

M4ID: 30008911

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.85 MAX_MED: -1.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Icaridin

CHID: 34227 CASRN: 119515-38-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A07

M4ID: 30008776

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	559.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.94 MAX_MED: 3.94 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Chlorophenoxyacetic acid

CHID: 34282 CASRN: 122-88-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N08

M4ID: 30009081

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.769 MAX_MED: 0.965 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Denatonium saccharide

CHID: 34361 CASRN: 90823-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D19

M4ID: 30008852

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.96 MAX_MED: 3.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Boscalid

CHID: 34392 CASRN: 188425-85-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B21

M4ID: 30008517

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	433.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.98 MAX_MED: 3.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Buprofezin

CHID: 34401 CASRN: 69327-76-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091003

M4ID: 30008352

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	565.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.72	MAX_MED: 6.68	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butachlor

CHID: 34402 CASRN: 23184-66-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P11

M4ID: 30008796

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	587.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.28 MAX_MED: 5.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cinmethylin

CHID: 34456 CASRN: 87818-31-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F20

M4ID: 30008370

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	613.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.89 MAX_MED: 7.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Metconazole

CHID: 34497 CASRN: 125116-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078011

M4ID: 30008568

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	585.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.79 MAX_MED: 4.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Desmedipham

CHID: 34518 CASRN: 13684-56-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M14

M4ID: 30008613

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.94 MAX_MED: 5.94 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diclosulam

CHID: 34528 CASRN: 145701-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K23

M4ID: 30008652

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	436.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.25 MAX_MED: 0.654 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Bromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone

CHID: 34576 CASRN: 2491-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D07

M4ID: 30008840

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.5 MAX_MED: 6.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluazifop-butyl

CHID: 34612 CASRN: 69806-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I17

M4ID: 30008970

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.71 MAX_MED: 5.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Flufenpyr-ethyl

CHID: 34618 CASRN: 188489-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I07

M4ID: 30008716

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.35 MAX_MED: 5.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluoxastrobin
 CHID: 34625 CASRN: 361377-29-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J05
 M4ID: 30008694

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	588.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.45 MAX_MED: 3.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Imazamox

CHID: 34664 CASRN: 114311-32-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J07

M4ID: 30008984

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.83 MAX_MED: 0.709 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isazofos

CHID: 34676 CASRN: 42509-80-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I18

M4ID: 30008971

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	492.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.29 MAX_MED: 2.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isoxaflutole

CHID: 34723 CASRN: 141112-29-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091024

M4ID: 30008807

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	402.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.35 MAX_MED: 1.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Milbemectin (mixture of 70% Milbemcin A4, 30% I

CHID: 34742 CASRN: NOCAS_34742

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D01

M4ID: 30008834

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 3.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Monocrotophos

CHID: 34816 CASRN: 6923-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091009

M4ID: 30008346

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	585.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.07 MAX_MED: 7.64 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propamocarb hydrochloride

CHID: 34849 CASRN: 25606-41-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F17

M4ID: 30008898

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	395.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.594 MAX_MED: 0.863 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluazifop-P-butyl

CHID: 34855 CASRN: 79241-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F09

M4ID: 30008890

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	552.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.08 MAX_MED: 6.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Chloridazon

CHID: 34872 CASRN: 1698-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E04

M4ID: 30008861

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	526.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.98 MAX_MED: 7.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyrimethanil

CHID: 34877 CASRN: 53112-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P04

M4ID: 30008803

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.22 MAX_MED: 2.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Spiromesifen

CHID: 34929 CASRN: 283594-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G01

M4ID: 30008813

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	609.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.23 MAX_MED: 1.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fosthiazate

CHID: 34930 CASRN: 98886-44-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091022

M4ID: 30008809

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	392.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.82 MAX_MED: 1.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Thiamethoxam

CHID: 34962 CASRN: 153719-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A17

M4ID: 30008540

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.35	MAX_MED:	5.93	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Thymo1

CHID: 34972 CASRN: 89-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E13

M4ID: 30008401

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	431.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.98 MAX_MED: 1.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tralkoxydim

CHID: 34973 CASRN: 87820-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L10

M4ID: 30009035

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	554.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.2 MAX_MED: 0.886 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium warfarin

CHID: 35010 CASRN: 129-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L17

M4ID: 30008634

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	432.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.88 MAX_MED: 2.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-(Hydroxymethyl)-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 35152 CASRN: 116-25-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D17

M4ID: 30008850

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	332.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.56 MAX_MED: 1.61 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: alpha-Ionone

CHID: 35160 CASRN: 127-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D14

M4ID: 30008424

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.15 MAX_MED: 4.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Allethrin

CHID: 35180 CASRN: 584-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P05

M4ID: 30008802

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.24 MAX_MED: 3.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Codlure

CHID: 35288 CASRN: 33956-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I01

M4ID: 30008722

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	654.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.13 MAX_MED: 5.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene

CHID: 35423 CASRN: 571-58-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K21

M4ID: 30008654

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	464.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.68 MAX_MED: 1.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Disiquonium chloride

CHID: 35589 CASRN: 68959-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J17

M4ID: 30008994

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	520.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.91 MAX_MED: 3.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-(8-Heptadecenyl)-2-imidazoline-1-ethanol

CHID: 36112 CASRN: 95-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K24

M4ID: 30009025

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.19 MAX_MED: 4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium decyl sulfate
 CHID: 36229 CASRN: 142-87-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H23
 M4ID: 30008952

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	342.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.78 MAX_MED: 2.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Citralva

CHID: 36286 CASRN: 5146-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F12

M4ID: 30008893

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.19 MAX_MED: 1.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Disodium 4,4'-bis(2-sulfostyryl)biphenyl

CHID: 36467 CASRN: 27344-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C12

M4ID: 30008821

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	488.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.35 MAX_MED: 4.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Amiodarone hydrochloride

CHID: 37185 CASRN: 19774-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091017

M4ID: 30008338

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.13 MAX_MED: 3.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Perfluoroheptanoic acid

CHID: 37303 CASRN: 375-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N16

M4ID: 30008363

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.325 MAX_MED: 0.801 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Deisopropylatrazine

CHID: 37495 CASRN: 1007-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E03

M4ID: 30008860

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	426.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.24 MAX_MED: 3.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fenuron

CHID: 37551 CASRN: 101-42-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K08

M4ID: 30008667

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	565.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.85 MAX_MED: 6.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate

CHID: 37709 CASRN: 3871-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091002

M4ID: 30008353

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	371.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.68 MAX_MED: 0.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5-Chlorosalicylanilide

CHID: 37749 CASRN: 4638-48-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I21

M4ID: 30008974

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	464.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.65 MAX_MED: 3.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzoic acid

CHID: 38321 CASRN: 3739-38-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M15

M4ID: 30009064

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	421.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.622 MAX_MED: 1.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Chlorpyrifos oxon

CHID: 38666 CASRN: 5598-15-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B10

M4ID: 30008528

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	530.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.29 MAX_MED: 5.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline

CHID: 38700 CASRN: 97-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G09

M4ID: 30008327

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.067 MAX_MED: 0.122 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid

CHID: 38788 CASRN: 1076-97-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H12

M4ID: 30008941

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	509.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.55 MAX_MED: 1.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Orange 7
 CHID: 38881 CASRN: 633-96-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091011
 M4ID: 30008344

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	547.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.28 MAX_MED: 0.845 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluorescein

CHID: 38887 CASRN: 2321-07-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D24

M4ID: 30008414

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.42 MAX_MED: 3.28 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Basic Blue 7

CHID: 38888 CASRN: 2390-60-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K11

M4ID: 30009012

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	581.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.03 MAX_MED: 0.455 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethyl propionate

CHID: 40110 CASRN: 105-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B03

M4ID: 30008483

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	562	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.3 MAX_MED: 4.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethyl butyrate

CHID: 40111 CASRN: 105-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H02

M4ID: 30008745

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	577.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.17 MAX_MED: 1.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethyl heptanoate

CHID: 40112 CASRN: 106-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I16

M4ID: 30008707

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	568.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.04	MAX_MED:	5.88	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Trifloxysulfuron-sodium

CHID: 40222 CASRN: 199119-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P23

M4ID: 30008784

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.73 MAX_MED: 2.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butylene carbonate

CHID: 40342 CASRN: 4437-85-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L19

M4ID: 30009044

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.31 MAX_MED: 2.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dinocap

CHID: 40352 CASRN: 39300-45-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E22

M4ID: 30008879

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	485.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.546 MAX_MED: 0.971 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isoxadifen-ethyl

CHID: 40360 CASRN: 163520-33-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H13

M4ID: 30008942

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.98 MAX_MED: 5.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Niclosamide
 CHID: 40362 CASRN: 50-65-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A24
 M4ID: 30008547

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	576.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.02 MAX_MED: 5.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Forskolin

CHID: 40484 CASRN: 66575-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J23

M4ID: 30009000

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	341.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.4 MAX_MED: 1.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butyl benzoate

CHID: 40694 CASRN: 136-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B15

M4ID: 30008523

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.4 MAX_MED: 3.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Trimethoxyphenylsilane

CHID: 40700 CASRN: 2996-92-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D16

M4ID: 30008849

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	407.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.97 MAX_MED: 2.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octyl gallate

CHID: 40713 CASRN: 1034-01-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K19

M4ID: 30009020

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.94 MAX_MED: 3.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Morin hydrate

CHID: 40776 CASRN: 654055-01-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C19

M4ID: 30008828

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 12 MAX_MED: 9.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-methoxyphenol

CHID: 40788 CASRN: 121-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B02

M4ID: 30008536

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	482.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.45 MAX_MED: 3.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyridoxine hydrochloride

CHID: 40792 CASRN: 58-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078009

M4ID: 30008570

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	526.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.129 MAX_MED: 0.0947 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium iodide
 CHID: 41125 CASRN: 7681-82-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L12
 M4ID: 30009037

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.49 MAX_MED: 0.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: (2-Nitro-1-propenyl)benzene

CHID: 41188 CASRN: 705-60-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F04

M4ID: 30008386

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.89	MAX_MED:	4.12	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3,5-Triisopropylbenzene

CHID: 41232 CASRN: 717-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G12

M4ID: 30008917

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	493.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.77 MAX_MED: 1.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone

CHID: 41252 CASRN: 128-95-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N07

M4ID: 30009080

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0126 MAX_MED: 0.244 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Hexyl-1-decanol

CHID: 41265 CASRN: 2425-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091012

M4ID: 30008343

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	599.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.92 MAX_MED: 2.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Phenyl-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione

CHID: 41274 CASRN: 941-69-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C01

M4ID: 30008461

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	626.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.84 MAX_MED: 4.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Monolaurin

CHID: 41275 CASRN: 142-18-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L23

M4ID: 30009048

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.24 MAX_MED: 5.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2'-Acetonaphthone
 CHID: 41389 CASRN: 93-08-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G22
 M4ID: 30008749

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.88 MAX_MED: 3.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: R-(-)-Carvone

CHID: 41413 CASRN: 6485-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E12

M4ID: 30008869

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	448.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.51 MAX_MED: 3.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 7-(Dimethylamino)-4-methylcoumarin

CHID: 41422 CASRN: 87-01-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D20

M4ID: 30008418

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	586.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.72 MAX_MED: 7.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Methylbutyl isovalerate

CHID: 41440 CASRN: 2445-77-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F11

M4ID: 30008379

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.77 MAX_MED: 4.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: (3Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate

CHID: 41484 CASRN: 3681-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E23

M4ID: 30008391

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	416.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0161 MAX_MED: 0.335 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenylhexane

CHID: 41492 CASRN: 4468-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I09

M4ID: 30008714

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.472 MAX_MED: 0.112 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: (4Z)-4-Decenal

CHID: 41514 CASRN: 21662-09-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K09

M4ID: 30008666

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	527.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.2 MAX_MED: 3.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Morpholinepropanamine

CHID: 41521 CASRN: 123-00-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B10

M4ID: 30008476

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	586.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.35 MAX_MED: 4.92 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 7-Ethyl-2-methyl-4-undecanoisulfate, sodium sa

CHID: 41530 CASRN: 139-88-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N19

M4ID: 30008360

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.71 MAX_MED: 4.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dihydromyrcenol

CHID: 41557 CASRN: 53219-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L16

M4ID: 30008635

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.65 MAX_MED: 6.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Arabinose

CHID: 41610 CASRN: 147-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C07

M4ID: 30008816

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	397.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.21 MAX_MED: 1.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium m-xylene-4-sulfonate

CHID: 41639 CASRN: 827-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G20

M4ID: 30008751

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.37 MAX_MED: 5.13 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 34, monosodium salt

CHID: 41646 CASRN: 6359-90-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E14

M4ID: 30008400

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.09 MAX_MED: 5.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxybenzonitrile

CHID: 41661 CASRN: 611-20-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G07

M4ID: 30008912

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	418.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.14 MAX_MED: 2.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bromophenol blue

CHID: 41682 CASRN: 115-39-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C02

M4ID: 30008460

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	728.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.85 MAX_MED: 6.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butylphthalenesulfonic acid sodium salt

CHID: 41703 CASRN: 25638-17-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F05

M4ID: 30008385

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.66 MAX_MED: 3.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Violet 12, disodium salt

CHID: 41715 CASRN: 6625-46-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K14

M4ID: 30008661

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.18 MAX_MED: 3.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 3 disodium salt

CHID: 41721 CASRN: 8004-92-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F14

M4ID: 30008895

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.207 MAX_MED: 0.446 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Citronella l

CHID: 41790 CASRN: 106-23-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C03

M4ID: 30008459

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.4 MAX_MED: 3.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dibutyl decanedioate

CHID: 41847 CASRN: 109-43-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E03

M4ID: 30008411

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	511.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.69 MAX_MED: 6.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethyl phosphite

CHID: 41861 CASRN: 762-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N15

M4ID: 30008588

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.57 MAX_MED: 3.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethyl diethanolamine
 CHID: 41955 CASRN: 139-87-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E19
 M4ID: 30008876

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.22 MAX_MED: 3.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethyl orthoformate
 CHID: 41957 CASRN: 122-51-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P05
 M4ID: 30008550

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	548.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.78 MAX_MED: 7.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Flufenoxuron

CHID: 41978 CASRN: 101463-69-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E01

M4ID: 30008413

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	673.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.98 MAX_MED: 3.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluoroacetic acid

CHID: 41981 CASRN: 144-49-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B20

M4ID: 30008518

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	481.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.72 MAX_MED: 3.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl monoricinoleate

CHID: 42007 CASRN: 1323-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M07

M4ID: 30008620

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	572.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.21 MAX_MED: 7.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isoborneol

CHID: 42060 CASRN: 124-76-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091021

M4ID: 30008810

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.62 MAX_MED: 3.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Dodecylmorpholine
 CHID: 42171 CASRN: 1541-81-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A23
 M4ID: 30008546

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	610.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.38 MAX_MED: 6.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Dibutylthiourea

CHID: 42187 CASRN: 109-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D12

M4ID: 30008845

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.14 MAX_MED: 3.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N-Diisopropylaniline

CHID: 42189 CASRN: 4107-98-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N08

M4ID: 30008595

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	539.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.21 MAX_MED: 5.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Dimethylthiourea
 CHID: 42191 CASRN: 534-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091016
 M4ID: 30008339

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.44 MAX_MED: 2.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butyl lactate

CHID: 42196 CASRN: 138-22-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A01

M4ID: 30008509

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	801.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	9.04	MAX_MED:	9.08	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Dodecyl-2-pyrrolidinone

CHID: 42206 CASRN: 2687-96-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M11

M4ID: 30008616

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	560.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.16 MAX_MED: 3.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Methyldioctylamine
 CHID: 42209 CASRN: 4455-26-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091010
 M4ID: 30008345

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	648.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 18.9 MAX_MED: 9.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propylbenzene
 CHID: 42219 CASRN: 103-65-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B11
 M4ID: 30008475

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.86 MAX_MED: 4.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Oleyl sarcosine

CHID: 42243 CASRN: 110-25-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I11

M4ID: 30008964

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	576.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.57 MAX_MED: 2.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethoxydimethylsilane

CHID: 42379 CASRN: 1112-39-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I12

M4ID: 30008965

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	502.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.3 MAX_MED: 1.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium (2-pyridylthio)-N-oxide

CHID: 42390 CASRN: 3811-73-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E11

M4ID: 30008403

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	522.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.38 MAX_MED: 3.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate

CHID: 42415 CASRN: 657-84-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C10

M4ID: 30008452

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.5 MAX_MED: 3.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sulfosuccinic acid

CHID: 42426 CASRN: 5138-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P19

M4ID: 30008788

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.79 MAX_MED: 6.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester

CHID: 42454 CASRN: 589-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E14

M4ID: 30008871

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	540.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.08 MAX_MED: 6.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Clove leaf oil

CHID: 44175 CASRN: 8000-34-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C09

M4ID: 30008453

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.13 MAX_MED: 2.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dibutyl-N-methylbutan-1-aminium chloride

CHID: 44443 CASRN: 56375-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P09

M4ID: 30008754

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	498.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.34 MAX_MED: 2.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-(6-tert-Butyl-1,1-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-im

CHID: 44536 CASRN: 13171-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M21

M4ID: 30009070

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	433.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.73 MAX_MED: 3.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: C.I. Disperse Orange 37

CHID: 44538 CASRN: 13301-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D23

M4ID: 30008856

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.6 MAX_MED: 3.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,6,10-Trimethyl-2,6,10-triazaundecane

CHID: 44564 CASRN: 3855-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L15

M4ID: 30009040

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05 MAX_MED: 2.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 6:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 44572 CASRN: 647-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D02

M4ID: 30008835

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.04 MAX_MED: 4.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: MON-4660

CHID: 44575 CASRN: 71526-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L13

M4ID: 30008638

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.047 MAX_MED: -0.207 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-ethylphenol

CHID: 44581 CASRN: 96-70-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N04

M4ID: 30009077

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	551.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.787 MAX_MED: -0.211 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Glycidyl trimethylammonium chloride

CHID: 44643 CASRN: 3033-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F21

M4ID: 30008902

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.192 MAX_MED: 0.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acid Red 337

CHID: 44713 CASRN: 67786-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L07

M4ID: 30009032

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	509.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0479 MAX_MED: 1.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Terpinyl propionate

CHID: 44833 CASRN: 80-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P15

M4ID: 30008760

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	605.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.26 MAX_MED: 6.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triallyl trimellitate

CHID: 44901 CASRN: 2694-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H11

M4ID: 30008940

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	646.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.2 MAX_MED: 8.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl triethanolamine titanate

CHID: 44928 CASRN: 36673-16-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C10

M4ID: 30008819

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.76 MAX_MED: 3.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octadecyl sulfate sodium salt

CHID: 47103 CASRN: 1120-04-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091013

M4ID: 30008342

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.72 MAX_MED: -1.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylbenzene

CHID: 47138 CASRN: 98-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F02

M4ID: 30008388

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	653.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.16 MAX_MED: 4.69 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Darbufelone mesylate

CHID: 47246 CASRN: 139340-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E01

M4ID: 30008858

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.65 MAX_MED: 5.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CI-1018

CHID: 47248 CASRN: NOCAS_47248

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F13

M4ID: 30008894

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.868 MAX_MED: -0.277 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-457920

CHID: 47254 CASRN: 220860-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N14

M4ID: 30008589

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.53 MAX_MED: 3.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Zamifenacin
 CHID: 47257 CASRN: 127308-82-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B24
 M4ID: 30008462

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	550.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.68 MAX_MED: 6.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_47263

CHID: 47263 CASRN: 349495-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078024

M4ID: 30008555

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	596.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.24 MAX_MED: 7.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Besonprodil

CHID: 47270 CASRN: 253450-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E02

M4ID: 30008412

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	711.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.65 MAX_MED: 4.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-409092

CHID: 47276 CASRN: 194098-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J01

M4ID: 30008698

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.51 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-457677

CHID: 47278 CASRN: 214535-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N01

M4ID: 30008602

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.78 MAX_MED: 4.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-607366

CHID: 47280 CASRN: 289716-94-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L01

M4ID: 30008650

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	688.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.67 MAX_MED: 1.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-671305

CHID: 47282 CASRN: 445295-04-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K07

M4ID: 30008668

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	597.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.12 MAX_MED: 7.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: PHA-00543613

CHID: 47284 CASRN: 478149-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H01

M4ID: 30008930

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	413.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.12 MAX_MED: 1.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: UK-416244

CHID: 47290 CASRN: 402910-27-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M13

M4ID: 30009062

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	466.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.206 MAX_MED: -0.0308 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-863187

CHID: 47294 CASRN: 668981-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J14

M4ID: 30008685

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.9 MAX_MED: 2.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-422935

CHID: 47299 CASRN: NOCAS_47299

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J01

M4ID: 30008978

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	382.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.98 MAX_MED: 1.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CP-608039

CHID: 47305 CASRN: NOCAS_47305

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M02

M4ID: 30008625

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	601.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.86 MAX_MED: 1.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: UK-156819

CHID: 47309 CASRN: 162706-14-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N09

M4ID: 30009082

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	545.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.456 MAX_MED: 0.384 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: GW473178E methyl benzene sulphonic acid

CHID: 47313 CASRN: 263553-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C13

M4ID: 30008822

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.07 MAX_MED: 3.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: MK-812

CHID: 47335 CASRN: 851916-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A18

M4ID: 30008541

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.62 MAX_MED: 6.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SR125047

CHID: 47342 CASRN: NOCAS_47342

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F01

M4ID: 30008389

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	662.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.41 MAX_MED: 2.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SSR162369

CHID: 47346 CASRN: NOCAS_47346

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C05

M4ID: 30008457

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	413.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.31 MAX_MED: 3.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SSR180711

CHID: 47359 CASRN: 298198-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P24

M4ID: 30008769

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.63 MAX_MED: 6.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SSR150106

CHID: 47362 CASRN: NOCAS_47362

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E15

M4ID: 30008399

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 11.8 MAX_MED: 9.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Volinanserin

CHID: 47363 CASRN: 139290-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P13

M4ID: 30008794

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0805 MAX_MED: -1.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SSR 103800

CHID: 47364 CASRN: 1075752-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P01

M4ID: 30008554

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	697.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.26 MAX_MED: 2.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: AVE3295

CHID: 47372 CASRN: 478263-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K02

M4ID: 30008673

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.96 MAX_MED: 1.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SAR377142

CHID: 47385 CASRN: NOCAS_47385

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N17

M4ID: 30008362

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	484.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.85 MAX_MED: 2.91 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Grinstad Soft-N-Safe

CHID: 47394 CASRN: NOCAS_47394

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078008

M4ID: 30008571

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	597.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.8 MAX_MED: 6.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate

CHID: 47395 CASRN: 166412-78-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B03

M4ID: 30008535

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.86 MAX_MED: 8.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Potassium chlorate
 CHID: 47448 CASRN: 3811-04-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H16
 M4ID: 30008945

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	476.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.644 MAX_MED: 1.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acid Yellow 11

CHID: 47451 CASRN: 6359-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A13

M4ID: 30008782

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.67 MAX_MED: 8.64 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexanedioic acid, di-C7-9-branched and linear ;

CHID: 47517 CASRN: 68515-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K09

M4ID: 30009010

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.2	MAX_MED: 4.46	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: C10-21 alkanesulfonic acids phenyl esters

CHID: 47526 CASRN: 91082-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B09

M4ID: 30008477

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	559.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.39 MAX_MED: 7.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Adipic acid, polypropyleneglycol, laurate

CHID: 47527 CASRN: 66456-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L08

M4ID: 30008643

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	479.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.9 MAX_MED: 9.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Trioctyl trimellitate
 CHID: 47533 CASRN: 89-04-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L03
 M4ID: 30009028

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	474.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.76 MAX_MED: 3.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Heptanolid

CHID: 47611 CASRN: 105-21-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J13

M4ID: 30008990

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.28 MAX_MED: 2.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cremophor EL

CHID: 47696 CASRN: 61791-12-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L02

M4ID: 30008649

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	702.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.15 MAX_MED: 5.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Igepal CO-890

CHID: 47708 CASRN: NOCAS_47708

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J08

M4ID: 30008691

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	604.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.44 MAX_MED: 6.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: FR167356

CHID: 48174 CASRN: 174185-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G05

M4ID: 30008910

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	527.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.22 MAX_MED: -0.938 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Melengestrol acetate

CHID: 48184 CASRN: 2919-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C15

M4ID: 30008447

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	556.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.86 MAX_MED: 6.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Lauryl gallate

CHID: 48189 CASRN: 1166-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H01

M4ID: 30008746

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	654.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.957 MAX_MED: 0.783 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl abietate

CHID: 48190 CASRN: 127-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I14

M4ID: 30008967

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	464.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.64	MAX_MED:	3.92	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Propylcyclohexanone

CHID: 48198 CASRN: 40649-36-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C14

M4ID: 30008448

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.07 MAX_MED: 5.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyclobutyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48201 CASRN: 5407-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078014

M4ID: 30008565

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	450.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.454 MAX_MED: 0.795 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48202 CASRN: 611-70-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G15

M4ID: 30008321

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.9 MAX_MED: 2.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloropentylbenzene

CHID: 48206 CASRN: 79098-20-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C14

M4ID: 30008823

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.02 MAX_MED: 3.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyl 2-methylbenzoate

CHID: 48208 CASRN: 89-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N04

M4ID: 30008599

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.07 MAX_MED: 4.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48505
 CHID: 48505 CASRN: NOCAS_48505
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078007
 M4ID: 30008572

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.09 MAX_MED: 5.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: HMR1171 trifluoroacetate (1:1)

CHID: 48522 CASRN: NOCAS_48522

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M08

M4ID: 30008619

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	575.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.7 MAX_MED: 5.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Amino-5-azotoluene
CHID: 20069 CASRN: 97-56-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F22
M4ID: 30008368 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.5e-09	2	2.94
sd:	7.61e-05	1020	80000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.53	-0.803	2.44	0.0882	11.4
sd:	59.1	12.9	144	5.11	499

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	781.44	787.44	790.36
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	19.46	19.46	19.41

MAX_MEAN: 4.07 MAX_MED: 4.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: (E)-Anethole

CHID: 20087 CASRN: 4180-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D05

M4ID: 30008433 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.98e-07	2.78	2.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.05	-0.179	0.3	0.0711	16.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	836.67	842.67	846.47
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	25.29	25.29	25.28

MAX_MEAN: 3.62 MAX_MED: 3.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Azobenzene
 CHID: 20123 CASRN: 103-33-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C12
 M4ID: 30008450 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.028 2.8 7.87
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.07 -3.4 6.81 0.57 15.7
 sd: 7.16 148 1440 17.3 8570

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	975.01	981.01	984.03
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	53.42	53.42	53.28

MAX_MEAN: 8.47 MAX_MED: 8.61 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Biphenyl
CHID: 20161 CASRN: 92-52-4
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I06
M4ID: 30008717 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
tp ga gw
val: 1.11e-07 2.76 1.32
sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
tp ga gw la lw
val: 1.92e-08 2.25 6.59 4.03 4.6
sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	893.81	899.81	903.81
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	38.33	38.33	38.33

MAX_MEAN: 5.23 MAX_MED: 4.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylhydroquinone
 CHID: 20220 CASRN: 1948-33-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C21
 M4ID: 30008441

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.66e-10 2.8 0.708
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.89 -0.106 0.3 0.144 3.55
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	638.9	644.9	648.51
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.95	7.95	7.94

MAX_MEAN: 2.04 MAX_MED: 1.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cupferron
 CHID: 20352 CASRN: 135-20-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D16
 M4ID: 30008422 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.0877 2.79 7.99
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.5e-09 2.29 3.4 3.13 4.25
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	831.72	837.72	841.72
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	26.07	26.07	26.07

MAX_MEAN: 8.27 MAX_MED: 7.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene

CHID: 20510 CASRN: 57-97-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E10

M4ID: 30008404

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.97e-09	2.14	0.553
sd:	3.89e-05	5570	7350

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.64e-09	1.46	1.68	1.74	5.62
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	660.95	666.95	670.95
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.51	9.51	9.51

MAX_MEAN: 1.34 MAX_MED: 1.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Endrin
 CHID: 20561 CASRN: 72-20-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F15
 M4ID: 30008896

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	763.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	15.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0526 MAX_MED: -0.495 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethoxyquin

CHID: 20582 CASRN: 91-53-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G19

M4ID: 30008317

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.22e-06	2.78	6.74
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.11	-3.67	6.49	-0.0185	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	691.87	697.87	696.86
PROB:	0.88	0.04	0.07
RMSE:	11.07	11.07	10.91

MAX_MEAN: 5.22 MAX_MED: 5.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.12

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Glycerol

CHID: 20663 CASRN: 56-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C17

M4ID: 30008445

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	670.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 25.8 MAX_MED: 23.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylhydrazine
CHID: 20710 CASRN: 122-66-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C15
M4ID: 30008824 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1014.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	65.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.297	MAX_MED:	-0.308	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,2'-Methylenebis(4-methyl-6-tert-butylphenol)

CHID: 20870 CASRN: 119-47-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P16

M4ID: 30008761

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 12.4 MAX_MED: 12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenediamine

CHID: 21137 CASRN: 108-45-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A21

M4ID: 30008489

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	599.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	14.1	MAX_MED:	10.5	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Quercetin
 CHID: 21218 CASRN: 117-39-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H15
 M4ID: 30008732 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.0498 2.8 7.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.86 0.283 0.3 0.54 5.71
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	836.72	842.72	846.25
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	24.87	24.87	24.84

MAX_MEAN: 4.65 MAX_MED: 4.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dichlorophen
 CHID: 21824 CASRN: 97-23-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N13
 M4ID: 30008366

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	643.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.29 MAX_MED: -1.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diphenylamine

CHID: 21975 CASRN: 122-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J18

M4ID: 30008681

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.02e-07	2.77	2.74
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.31	-1.54	0.3	0.00145	1.73
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	720.87	726.87	728.37
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	13.33	13.33	13.24

MAX_MEAN: 4.88 MAX_MED: 4.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dibenzofuran
CHID: 21993 CASRN: 132-64-9
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P14
M4ID: 30008793 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.34e-08	2.74	1.18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.53e-09	2.18	1.64	2.59	5.79
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	829.06	835.06	839.06
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	26.08	26.08	26.08

MAX_MEAN: 1.93 MAX_MED: 1.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Flavone
 CHID: 22048 CASRN: 525-82-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G11
 M4ID: 30008916 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.13e-09 2.48 1.52
 sd: 5.45e-05 4680 29900

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.37e-08 2.12 1.69 2.41 5.88
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	627.03	633.03	637.03
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	17.41	17.41	17.41

MAX_MEAN: 2.21 MAX_MED: 1.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: gamma-Decanolactone
CHID: 22109 CASRN: 706-14-9
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D17
M4ID: 30008421

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	566.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 17 MAX_MED: 15.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triphenylethylene
CHID: 22320 CASRN: 58-72-0
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K06
M4ID: 30009007 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
tp ga gw
val: 6.03e-06 2.77 5
sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
tp ga gw la lw
val: 1.42e-07 0.126 7.99 0.411 7.81
sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	837.8	843.8	847.8
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	24.18	24.18	24.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.619 MAX_MED: 8.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,1,1-trichloroethane

CHID: 22325 CASRN: 2971-36-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B06

M4ID: 30008532

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.47e-08	2.68	3.68
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.68e-09	2.29	4.69	3.83	17.6
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	690.29	696.29	700.29
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.58	11.58	11.58

MAX_MEAN: 13 MAX_MED: 10.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 17alpha-Estradiol

CHID: 22377 CASRN: 57-91-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K06

M4ID: 30008669

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	854.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	26.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	42	MAX_MED:	49.1	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10; 8

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phenolphthalin

CHID: 22439 CASRN: 81-90-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N05

M4ID: 30009078

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.21e-09	2	1.15
sd:	5.46e-05	928	14400

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.03e-10	1.78	1.58	2.37	4.94
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	661.84	667.84	671.84
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.37	11.37	11.37

MAX_MEAN: 0.139 MAX_MED: 0.536 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butanal oxime

CHID: 24664 CASRN: 110-69-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A12

M4ID: 30008498

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	687.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.8 MAX_MED: 10.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl succinate
 CHID: 25152 CASRN: 106-65-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A24
 M4ID: 30008486

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	628.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.2 MAX_MED: 10.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Maltol

CHID: 25523 CASRN: 118-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B21

M4ID: 30008465

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	555.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.66 MAX_MED: 10.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Nitroaniline
 CHID: 25726 CASRN: 88-74-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N01
 M4ID: 30009074

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.87e-09	2.18	1.34
sd:	2.02e-05	1970	14100

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.7e-10	1.53	2.72	1.84	4.86
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	618.55	624.55	628.55
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.97	7.97	7.97

MAX_MEAN: 0.71 MAX_MED: 0.746 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octhilinone

CHID: 25805 CASRN: 26530-20-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L06

M4ID: 30009031

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	672.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.27 MAX_MED: -1.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-pentylphenol

CHID: 26974 CASRN: 120-95-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L16

M4ID: 30009041

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	604.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.05 MAX_MED: -1.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Naphthalenol
 CHID: 27061 CASRN: 135-19-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K10
 M4ID: 30008665

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.76e-08	2.57	0.844
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.57e-08	1.86	1.94	2.18	5.72
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	664.51	670.51	674.51
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.56	10.56	10.56

MAX_MEAN: 0.841 MAX_MED: 1.44 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Methylphthalimide
 CHID: 27198 CASRN: 550-44-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P08
 M4ID: 30008753

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	624.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.2 MAX_MED: 11.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Malic acid
 CHID: 27640 CASRN: 6915-15-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P12
 M4ID: 30008757

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	663.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.2 MAX_MED: 10.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dodecylphenol

CHID: 27926 CASRN: 27193-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B19

M4ID: 30008519 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.125	2.8	7.96
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.45	-2.7	5.32	0.78	18
sd:	2.29	0.305	8510	0.901	81.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	778.05	784.05	784.05
PROB:	0.91	0.05	0.05
RMSE:	20.04	20.04	19.89

MAX_MEAN: 6.41 MAX_MED: 8.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.09

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Iodo-2-propynyl-N-butylcarbamate

CHID: 28038 CASRN: 55406-53-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M23

M4ID: 30008604

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.03e-10	2.56	0.627
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.66e-09	0.0119	3.5	0.344	5.74
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.11	596.11	600.11
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.05	6.05	6.05

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 1.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,1-Bis(3,4-dimethylphenyl)ethane

CHID: 29223 CASRN: 1742-14-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B16

M4ID: 30008470

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	603.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 12.3 MAX_MED: 12.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acetyl cedrene

CHID: 29353 CASRN: 32388-55-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B17

M4ID: 30008469

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	734.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	14.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 32 MAX_MED: 24.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

-42
-63

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butralin

CHID: 32337 CASRN: 33629-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C17

M4ID: 30008826 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.68e-09	1.5	1.59
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.61e-09	1.41	1.53	1.91	5.81
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	849.65	855.65	859.65
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	26.37	26.37	26.37

MAX_MEAN: 1.11 MAX_MED: 1.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triclosan
 CHID: 32498 CASRN: 3380-34-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091006
 M4ID: 30008349

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	581.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.498 MAX_MED: -0.728 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Flufenacet
 CHID: 32552 CASRN: 142459-58-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N16
 M4ID: 30008587

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	560.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.64 MAX_MED: 10.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Trifloxystrobin

CHID: 32580 CASRN: 141517-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J24

M4ID: 30009001

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.01e-10	1.02	1.47
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.71	-0.242	7.92	0.0497	11.8
sd:	212	56.4	648	12.8	713

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	600.24	606.24	608.61
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.61	6.61	6.58

MAX_MEAN: 2.13 MAX_MED: 1.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pyriproxyfen
 CHID: 32640 CASRN: 95737-68-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G21
 M4ID: 30008926

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.11e-07 2.79 5.77
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.8 0.551 0.52 0.801 17.9
 sd: 35.3 11.6 1.8 2.82 254

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	704.09	710.09	712.96
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.69	11.69	11.65

MAX_MEAN: 2.63 MAX_MED: 3.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Nonylphenol

CHID: 33836 CASRN: 104-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F10

M4ID: 30008891 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.64e-09	2.75	2.86
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.23	0.887	0.517	1.14	18
sd:	110	28.6	3.31	0.749	86.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	695.77	701.77	702.82
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.03
RMSE:	12.42	12.42	12.34

MAX_MEAN: 3.58 MAX_MED: 4.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexaconazole

CHID: 34653 CASRN: 79983-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078003

M4ID: 30008576

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.542 MAX_MED: -0.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Azamethiphos

CHID: 34818 CASRN: 35575-96-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K03

M4ID: 30009004

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.31e-09	2.25	1.6
sd:	1.98e-05	2980	26900

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.97e-09	1.85	2.14	2.77	5.18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	621.17	627.17	631.17
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8	8	8

MAX_MEAN: 0.978 MAX_MED: 1.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methylbenzethonium chloride

CHID: 35708 CASRN: 25155-18-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D10

M4ID: 30008843

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.87e-09	1.58	1.51
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.92	-3.7	6.25	0.265	16.7
sd:	1.15	431	2700	15.4	862

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	642.81	648.81	650.12
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	8.68	8.68	8.62

MAX_MEAN: 2.64 MAX_MED: 2.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide

CHID: 37028 CASRN: 57-09-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J13

M4ID: 30008686

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.38e-08	2.7	1.93
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.83	0.0603	0.3	0.513	2.66
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	576.91	582.91	584.26
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	6.15	6.15	6.11

MAX_MEAN: 2.44 MAX_MED: 2.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Potassium perfluorooctanesulfonate
 CHID: 37706 CASRN: 2795-39-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E06
 M4ID: 30008863

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.14e-08 2.74 1.63
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.36 1.29 7.99 1.54 17.6
 sd: 21.8 1.07 24.1 1.64 183

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	604.88	610.88	614.18
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.8	7.8	7.79

MAX_MEAN: 2.29 MAX_MED: 4.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diniconazole
 CHID: 40363 CASRN: 83657-24-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C06
 M4ID: 30008815

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.77e-09 2.05 2.94
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.52 0.804 8 1.05 14
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	620.3	626.3	625.83
PROB:	0.9	0.04	0.06
RMSE:	7.26	7.26	7.09

MAX_MEAN: 5.13 MAX_MED: 4.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5-Ethyl-5-methylhydantoin

CHID: 41368 CASRN: 5394-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C16

M4ID: 30008446

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	620.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.9 MAX_MED: 11.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethylbenzylcarbinyyl acetate

CHID: 41877 CASRN: 151-05-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L15

M4ID: 30008636 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.06e-09	2.75	3.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.59e-10	2.29	5.77	3.65	5.78
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	807.7	813.7	817.7
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	23.19	23.19	23.19

MAX_MEAN: 3.96 MAX_MED: 3.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Butyl-p-toluenesulfonamide

CHID: 42198 CASRN: 1907-65-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A16

M4ID: 30008494

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	694.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 14.4 MAX_MED: 15.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Methyltrioctylammonium chloride

CHID: 44487 CASRN: 5137-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A09

M4ID: 30008501

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.000237	2.8	7.16
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.48	-1.21	7.08	0.00623	11.2
sd:	111	50	1730	1.66	879

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	684.8	690.8	690.35
PROB:	0.9	0.04	0.06
RMSE:	10.23	10.23	10.05

MAX_MEAN: 6.52 MAX_MED: 8.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,2'-(Tetradecylimino)diethanol
 CHID: 44865 CASRN: 18924-66-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D10
 M4ID: 30008428

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.3e-06 2.79 4.81
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.2 0.438 0.3 1.29 16.1
 sd: 61.4 25.6 1.77 0.14 325

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	696.89	702.89	699.46
PROB:	0.75	0.04	0.21
RMSE:	12.28	12.28	12.07

MAX_MEAN: 4.63 MAX_MED: 6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.25

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CI-959
 CHID: 47268 CASRN: 104795-68-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J09
 M4ID: 30008986

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.103 2.8 7.97
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.26 0.689 0.3 0.94 1.19
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	627.9	633.9	632.65
PROB:	0.88	0.04	0.08
RMSE:	9.16	9.16	9.02

MAX_MEAN: 6.92 MAX_MED: 10.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.12

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 9-Phenanthroline
 CHID: 47592 CASRN: 484-17-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L04
 M4ID: 30008647

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.79e-10 1.51 1.86
 sd: 5.26e-06 2730 81100

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.2e-06 -0.536 4.41 -0.282 7.21
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	654.14	660.14	664.14
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.08	9.08	9.08

MAX_MEAN: 3.93 MAX_MED: 2.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Sulfonylbis[2-(prop-2-en-1-yl)phenol]

CHID: 47598 CASRN: 41481-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I05

M4ID: 30008958

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.29e-08	2.63	2.02
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.03	1.23	5.04	1.69	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	552.62	558.62	560.39
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	5.27	5.27	5.28

MAX_MEAN: 1.7 MAX_MED: 3.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene
 CHID: 21402 CASRN: 95-63-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I08
 M4ID: 30008961 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.46 0.42 8
 sd: 0.937 1.89 51.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.37 0.317 8 0.567 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	801.24	804.69	811.04
PROB:	0.84	0.15	0.01
RMSE:	33.29	33.06	33.25

MAX_MEAN: 39.2 MAX_MED: 23.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 9 ACTP: 0.16

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Resmethrin

CHID: 22253 CASRN: 10453-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H03

M4ID: 30008932

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.98e-08	2.64	2.82
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.58	1.02	1.44	1.27	10.6
sd:	35	2.12	2.67	0.335	107

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	631.12	637.12	633.46
PROB:	0.74	0.04	0.23
RMSE:	8.55	8.55	8.36

MAX_MEAN: 4.79 MAX_MED: 3.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 9 ACTP: 0.26

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Dodecylphenol
 CHID: 22508 CASRN: 104-43-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A11
 M4ID: 30008780 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.2e-07	2.78	1.07
sd:	0.000211	5680	11500

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.6	-0.242	0.3	1.09	16.8
sd:	93.3	24.2	1.7	1.74	144

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	776.77	782.77	778.06
PROB:	0.64	0.03	0.33
RMSE:	20.97	20.97	20.7

MAX_MEAN: 7.66 MAX_MED: 9.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.36

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Butylbenzenesulfonamide

CHID: 27540 CASRN: 3622-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H09

M4ID: 30008938

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	58.2	2.8	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	64.5	1.99	8	2.24	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	698.55	704.55	725.75
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0
RMSE:	24.41	24.41	18.82

MAX_MEAN: 53.4 MAX_MED: 57.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid

CHID: 37730 CASRN: 31519-22-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L09

M4ID: 30008642

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.57e-07	2.77	3.01
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	30	1.37	8	1.65	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	655.41	661.41	659.46
PROB:	0.85	0.04	0.11
RMSE:	9.04	9.04	8.6

MAX_MEAN: 7.01 MAX_MED: 4.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.15

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanedione

CHID: 41247 CASRN: 120-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A17

M4ID: 30008493 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.38e-08	2.45	1.88
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	71.4	0.288	0.3	0.544	2.65
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1054.36	1060.36	1058.72
PROB:	0.86	0.04	0.1
RMSE:	80.88	80.88	79.46

MAX_MEAN: 38.9 MAX_MED: 41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.14

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-(Methylthio)propanal

CHID: 27528 CASRN: 3268-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A20

M4ID: 30008543

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.71	-3.35	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.72	-3.34	0.3	4.3	3.77
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	640.1	546.69	550.88
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	8.02	4.75	4.75

MAX_MEAN: 9.36 MAX_MED: 10.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Cyhalofop-butyl

CHID: 34503 CASRN: 122008-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E21

M4ID: 30008393

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.49	0.364	2.14
sd:	0.838	0.258	1.41

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.49	0.364	2.14	3.34	6.19
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	634.69	572.14	576.14
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.83	5.28	5.28

MAX_MEAN: 9.05 MAX_MED: 10.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 22406 CASRN: 131-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D24

M4ID: 30008857

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.42	1.93	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.97	0.0465	1.18	4.21	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	645.5	632.38	634.52
PROB:	0	0.74	0.26
RMSE:	9.58	8.44	8.41

MAX_MEAN: 11.1 MAX_MED: 10.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 18 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propham

CHID: 20766 CASRN: 122-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A10

M4ID: 30008500

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.74	-1.47	0.3
sd:	3.35	1.71	0.349

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.74	-1.46	0.3	4.24	17.2
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	662.17	592.62	596.62
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.88	5.9	5.9

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 11.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzothiazole
 CHID: 24586 CASRN: 95-16-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A02
 M4ID: 30008508

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.74	-2.82	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.74	-2.82	0.3	4.24	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	874.28	655.56	659.55
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.37	3.45	3.45

MAX_MEAN: 9.64 MAX_MED: 10 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzyloctyl adipate

CHID: 47528 CASRN: 58394-64-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B14

M4ID: 30008524

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8	0.981	1.6
sd:	2.06	0.29	1.99

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8	0.981	1.6	3.66	5.77
sd:	2.06	0.29	1.98	1440	6070

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	611.1	516.62	520.62
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.88	4.08	4.08

MAX_MEAN: 10.3 MAX_MED: 10.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloro-1,2-diaminobenzene

CHID: 20283 CASRN: 95-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M06

M4ID: 30009055

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.88	1.58	1.84
sd:	1.85	0.152	0.674

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.8	1.85	1.41	2.33	17.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.99	513.36	516.82
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	6.6	4.06	4.06

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 10.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phenothiazine
 CHID: 21126 CASRN: 92-84-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D19
 M4ID: 30008419

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.62e-07 2.7 3.07
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.28 -3.63 7.43 1.5 18
 sd: 0.609 302 2420 1.3 118

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.49	599.49	590.96
PROB:	0.22	0.01	0.77
RMSE:	7.18	7.18	6.97

MAX_MEAN: 4.35 MAX_MED: 4.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.78

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tromethamine
 CHID: 23723 CASRN: 77-86-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M15
 M4ID: 30008612

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0017	2.8	7.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.92	-0.865	4.9	0.494	1.61
sd:	3.05	5.34	193	0.539	1.28

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.77	585.77	578.65
PROB:	0.36	0.02	0.63
RMSE:	6.56	6.56	6.39

MAX_MEAN: 4.18 MAX_MED: 4.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.64

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benz(a)anthracene

CHID: 23902 CASRN: 56-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K02

M4ID: 30009003

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.72	-3.7	7.33
sd:	0.306	322	2370

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.93	-3.66	6.87	1.02	16.5
sd:	0.291	145	1040	0.413	299

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.34	147.02	144.43
PROB:	0	0.21	0.78
RMSE:	3.35	3.21	2.88

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 2.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol
 CHID: 26602 CASRN: 96-76-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C24
 M4ID: 30008438

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.0212 2.8 7.97
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.55 -3.6 7.69 1.35 15.6
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	640.15	646.15	639.24
PROB:	0.38	0.02	0.6
RMSE:	9.21	9.21	8.99

MAX_MEAN: 5.01 MAX_MED: 3.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.62

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Ethofumesate

CHID: 34580 CASRN: 26225-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K17

M4ID: 30009018

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.18e-08	2.79	2.41
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.35	-3.6	7.42	1.13	18
sd:	0.572	316	2600	0.583	69.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	553.86	559.86	548.55
PROB:	0.07	0	0.93
RMSE:	5.1	5.1	4.81

MAX_MEAN: 3.28 MAX_MED: 3.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.93

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Cyclohexylcyclohexanone

CHID: 40721 CASRN: 92-68-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F12

M4ID: 30008378

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.17	-3.67	7.1
sd:	0.425	302	2210

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.22	-3.49	7.46	1.9	18
sd:	0.405	145	1370	0.0316	32.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	575.25	541.11	513.84
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	5.87	5.55	4.64

MAX_MEAN: 5.4 MAX_MED: 5.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Sodium tridecyl sulfate
 CHID: 42418 CASRN: 3026-63-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P04
 M4ID: 30008551

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0248	2.8	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.88	-3.66	7.47	1.26	16.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	620.25	626.25	608.62
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.48	7.48	6.9

MAX_MEAN: 7.68 MAX_MED: 5.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylethanone

CHID: 44430 CASRN: 451-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L20

M4ID: 30008631

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.32	-3.7	1.71
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5	-3.7	0.3	2.15	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.5	542.17	536.4
PROB:	0	0.05	0.95
RMSE:	7.06	5.83	5.18

MAX_MEAN: 9.29 MAX_MED: 10.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SAR 150640

CHID: 47389 CASRN: 433212-21-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M17

M4ID: 30009066

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.49e-06	2.72	7.27
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.22	-1.05	0.3	1.69	18
sd:	7.72	4.58	0.586	0.0351	43.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	631.82	637.82	608.94
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.83	7.83	7.1

MAX_MEAN: 6.08 MAX_MED: 6.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Butylphenol
 CHID: 47425 CASRN: 1638-22-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M09
 M4ID: 30008618

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.92	0.337	8
sd:	1.29	0.991	25.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.8	0.594	7.98	1.7	18
sd:	1.92	0.12	103	0.0443	52.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	696.9	695.13	689.17
PROB:	0.02	0.05	0.93
RMSE:	11.89	12.31	11.29

MAX_MEAN: 8.04 MAX_MED: 8.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Endosulfan
 CHID: 20560 CASRN: 115-29-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G03
 M4ID: 30008908

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.19e-06 2.8 5.09
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 12.2 1.02 7.92 1.28 17.8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	591.9	597.9	588.97
PROB:	0.19	0.01	0.8
RMSE:	6.53	6.53	6.2

MAX_MEAN: 5.03 MAX_MED: 6.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 0.81

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Molinate
 CHID: 24206 CASRN: 2212-67-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I13
 M4ID: 30008710

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 11.4 1.64 1.67
 sd: 1.52 0.109 0.458

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 18.9 1.97 1.28 2.34 12
 sd: 18 0.622 0.537 0.0271 14

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	594.17	459.7	462.3
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	6.38	2.88	2.86

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pendimethalin
 CHID: 24245 CASRN: 40487-42-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P20
 M4ID: 30008787

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.4	0.186	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.2	0.989	0.3	2.33	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	642.63	557.28	560.24
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	7.98	5.12	5.04

MAX_MEAN: 10.2 MAX_MED: 10.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Chloro-1,2-propanediol

CHID: 20664 CASRN: 96-24-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I09

M4ID: 30008962

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	28.9	-2.59	7.85
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	28.9	-2.59	7.73	3.41	10.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	888.68	735.97	739.97
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	31	13.52	13.52

MAX_MEAN: 37.6 MAX_MED: 42.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diphenolic acid

CHID: 22436 CASRN: 126-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L13

M4ID: 30009038

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	23.7	1.32	1.96
sd:	1.69	0.0674	0.416

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	25.7	1.38	1.69	2.4	8.03
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	762.93	551.09	553.83
PROB:	0	0.8	0.2
RMSE:	16.48	5.49	5.43

MAX_MEAN: 29.1 MAX_MED: 27.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diphenyl phosphite

CHID: 41889 CASRN: 4712-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E20

M4ID: 30008877

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.7	0.443	0.866
sd:	2.81	0.312	0.538

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.7	0.443	0.865	3.73	8.16
sd:	2.81	0.312	0.538	78700	430000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	727.44	608.29	612.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	13.09	6.63	6.63

MAX_MEAN: 19.2 MAX_MED: 18.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Zenarestat
 CHID: 47296 CASRN: 112733-06-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L24
 M4ID: 30008627

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.9	1.74	2.64
sd:	3.32	0.0852	1.03

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	31.1	1.99	1.82	2.37	3.02
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	648.07	504.59	507.51
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	9.16	3.98	3.99

MAX_MEAN: 16.6 MAX_MED: 15.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzyl butyl phthalate

CHID: 20205 CASRN: 85-68-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P16

M4ID: 30008791

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	80.4	1.52	1.56
sd:	1.73	0.0208	0.0717

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	80.4	1.52	1.56	3.12	11.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	939.68	503.09	507.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	42.97	3.81	3.81

MAX_MEAN: 75.4 MAX_MED: 75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Carbofuran

CHID: 20249 CASRN: 1563-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P06

M4ID: 30008549

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	91.4	2	0.742
sd:	20.8	0.271	0.108

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	91.4	2	0.749	2.44	13.1
sd:	34.2	0.392	0.117	0.26	23.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	883.44	644.64	648.61
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	31.94	8.94	8.91

MAX_MEAN: 56.6 MAX_MED: 58.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane
 CHID: 20375 CASRN: 50-29-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E17
 M4ID: 30008874

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 34.2 2.35 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 20.4 2.3 8 3.87 3.98
 sd: 57.2 0.304 5.4 1380 3540

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	609.47	601.92	605.97
PROB:	0.02	0.87	0.11
RMSE:	8.25	7.58	7.58

MAX_MEAN: 10.4 MAX_MED: 11.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,4-D Butyl ester

CHID: 20443 CASRN: 94-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H13

M4ID: 30008734

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.7	1.37	1.01
sd:	2.2	0.175	0.23

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.7	1.37	1.01	4.3	6.01
sd:	2.2	0.175	0.23	711000	1390000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	658.37	446.23	450.23
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.85	2.65	2.65

MAX_MEAN: 14.2 MAX_MED: 14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol
 CHID: 20462 CASRN: 111-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F18
 M4ID: 30008372

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.9	2.8	0.306
sd:	15.5	2.21	0.163

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.3	2.3	0.3	3.58	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	583.93	505.55	509.95
PROB:	0	0.9	0.1
RMSE:	5.97	3.81	3.82

MAX_MEAN: 11 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nitrilotriacetic acid
 CHID: 20939 CASRN: 139-13-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A22
 M4ID: 30008488

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	46	2.36	0.3
sd:	43.3	2.51	0.13

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	39.1	1.94	0.318	3.26	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	769	622.54	626.97
PROB:	0	0.9	0.1
RMSE:	16.21	7.21	7.22

MAX_MEAN: 22.2 MAX_MED: 24.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nitrofurantoin
 CHID: 20972 CASRN: 67-20-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H02
 M4ID: 30008931

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.7	1.33	0.713
sd:	24.9	4.66	1.78

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.7	1.33	0.713	3.79	17.7
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.08	131.67	135.67
PROB:	0.02	0.86	0.12
RMSE:	3	2.11	2.11

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodibutylamine
 CHID: 21026 CASRN: 924-16-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J15
 M4ID: 30008992

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	32.4	2.1	1.2
sd:	5.75	0.137	0.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	32.4	2.1	1.2	3.69	6.96
sd:	5.75	0.137	0.198	3460	17300

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	668.78	476	480
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.14	3.15	3.14

MAX_MEAN: 22.1 MAX_MED: 21.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Thiabendazole

CHID: 21337 CASRN: 148-79-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A05

M4ID: 30008774

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.1	-0.316	0.3
sd:	4.74	1.29	0.188

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.1	-0.317	0.3	3.29	15
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	695.95	598.7	602.7
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.97	6.48	6.48

MAX_MEAN: 12.1 MAX_MED: 13.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octanoic acid

CHID: 21645 CASRN: 124-07-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P07

M4ID: 30008752

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	33.2	2.02	0.719
sd:	6.75	0.249	0.146

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	33.2	2.02	0.72	3.18	10.8
sd:	6.76	0.249	0.146	1170	14400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	710.91	542.16	546.16
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.85	4.58	4.58

MAX_MEAN: 22.7 MAX_MED: 22.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfoxide
 CHID: 21735 CASRN: 67-68-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B11
 M4ID: 30008527

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	61.3	2.62	0.797
sd:	57.2	0.84	0.211

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	43.3	2.3	0.894	2.67	16
sd:	27	0.559	0.242	38.4	1580

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	686.72	592.78	597.14
PROB:	0	0.9	0.1
RMSE:	12.45	7.87	7.88

MAX_MEAN: 21.1 MAX_MED: 23.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Methyl-2,4-pentanedio1

CHID: 21885 CASRN: 107-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H07

M4ID: 30008740

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	38.6	2.33	0.87
sd:	18.3	0.454	0.255

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	38	2.3	0.898	4.27	17.3
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	669.1	542.44	546.52
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.12	4.6	4.6

MAX_MEAN: 19.8 MAX_MED: 19.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Phenyl salicylate
 CHID: 21957 CASRN: 118-55-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L19
 M4ID: 30008632

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.6	1.95	0.701
sd:	8.7	0.315	0.142

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.6	1.93	0.721	2.38	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	719.98	542.86	546.79
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	12.86	4.72	4.7

MAX_MEAN: 21.6 MAX_MED: 23.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Phenoxyethanol
 CHID: 21976 CASRN: 122-99-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C22
 M4ID: 30008440

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 31.4 2.8 0.401
 sd: 42.9 2.36 0.146

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 23.7 2.3 0.431 3.57 6.15
 sd: 23.6 1.76 0.158 867 4210

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	648.65	584.16	588.41
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	8.87	5.9	5.91

MAX_MEAN: 13.3 MAX_MED: 14.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Diaminobiphenyl methane

CHID: 22422 CASRN: 101-77-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P18

M4ID: 30008763

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	21.8	2.47	0.3
sd:	17.6	2.23	0.288

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	20.2	2.3	0.3	2.98	10.4
sd:	15	1.98	0.339	230	3490

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	670.26	582.2	586.34
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	10.41	6.69	6.71

MAX_MEAN: 21.8 MAX_MED: 21.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Polydimethylsiloxane
 CHID: 23833 CASRN: 9016-00-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A12
 M4ID: 30008781

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	37.3	2.18	0.823
sd:	15.4	0.42	0.189

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	37.3	2.14	0.887	2.39	10
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	690.34	513.68	516.86
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	11.06	4.06	4.07

MAX_MEAN: 20.8 MAX_MED: 20.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Terbaci1

CHID: 24317 CASRN: 5902-51-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K05

M4ID: 30008670

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	27.8	2.07	1
sd:	5.81	0.19	0.198

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.8	2.07	1	4.3	5.44
sd:	5.81	0.19	0.198	21600	58500

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	657.05	474.84	478.84
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.08	3.11	3.11

MAX_MEAN: 18.4 MAX_MED: 18.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Troclosesene

CHID: 24993 CASRN: 2782-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A19

M4ID: 30008542

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.8	1.26	0.3
sd:	13.4	2.85	0.241

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	20.7	2.3	0.3	3.89	7.56
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	671.79	624.12	627.52
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	10.21	7.62	7.59

MAX_MEAN: 12.6 MAX_MED: 13.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dicyclopentadiene

CHID: 25023 CASRN: 77-73-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E04

M4ID: 30008410

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	53.3	2.59	0.562
sd:	26.6	0.65	0.109

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	43.1	2.3	0.609	4.3	5.53
sd:	21.7	0.635	0.125	27400	76000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	724.28	581.25	586.04
PROB:	0	0.92	0.08
RMSE:	13.82	6.71	6.7

MAX_MEAN: 23.4 MAX_MED: 25.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Triphenyl phosphite
 CHID: 26252 CASRN: 101-02-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H17
 M4ID: 30008946

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 22.4 2.31 0.699
 sd: 7.01 0.359 0.158

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 22.4 2.3 0.714 3.97 17.6
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	594.94	462.14	466.16
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.54	2.93	2.93

MAX_MEAN: 12.2 MAX_MED: 12.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3,7-Dimethyl-3-octanol

CHID: 29110 CASRN: 78-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F13

M4ID: 30008377

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	21.7	2.14	1.14
sd:	8.47	0.305	0.328

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	21.7	2.13	1.18	2.39	17.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	596.1	462.26	466.22
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.61	2.86	2.86

MAX_MEAN: 13.1 MAX_MED: 12.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 8:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol
 CHID: 29904 CASRN: 678-39-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E02
 M4ID: 30008859

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13.9 1.84 0.485
 sd: 2.93 0.384 0.0912

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 13.9 1.84 0.485 3.75 5.86
 sd: 2.92 0.383 0.0914 824 3330

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.47	399.45	403.45
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.66	2.02	2.02

MAX_MEAN: 9.98 MAX_MED: 10.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Clodinafop-propargyl

CHID: 32354 CASRN: 105512-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B04

M4ID: 30008534

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.7	1.49	0.468
sd:	2.96	0.32	0.0772

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	18.7	1.49	0.468	4.11	4.3
sd:	2.96	0.32	0.0773	1620	3590

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	661.15	400.69	404.69
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.72	2.21	2.21

MAX_MEAN: 13.1 MAX_MED: 13.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Clomazone
 CHID: 32355 CASRN: 81777-89-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P09
 M4ID: 30008798

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 20.1 1.62 1.38
 sd: 4.1 0.172 0.523

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 35.6 2.03 1.1 2.32 17.5
 sd: 37.6 0.725 0.377 0.0239 24.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	700.7	590.31	590.88
PROB:	0	0.57	0.43
RMSE:	11.36	5.92	5.82

MAX_MEAN: 18.3 MAX_MED: 18.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Amino-1,2,4-triazole
 CHID: 33058 CASRN: 584-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P24
 M4ID: 30008783

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.8	1.87	2.79
sd:	1.14	0.0387	0.771

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.8	1.87	2.79	4.3	6.2
sd:	1.14	0.0387	0.771	84600	290000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	572.91	405.26	409.26
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.78	2.16	2.16

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 11.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 17-Methyltestosterone

CHID: 33664 CASRN: 58-18-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A14

M4ID: 30008537

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	47	0.84	0.3
sd:	39.7	2.73	0.251

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	56.9	1.34	0.3	2.32	17.9
sd:	68.9	3.61	0.233	0.0177	22.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	879.25	732.01	732.18
PROB:	0	0.52	0.48
RMSE:	30.21	13.38	13.17

MAX_MEAN: 44.3 MAX_MED: 43.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Tepra loxydim

CHID: 34252 CASRN: 149979-41-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C09

M4ID: 30008818

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	60.9	2.26	4.51
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	60.9	2.26	4.51	4.3	4.17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	600.5	570.28	574.28
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.01	9.22	9.22

MAX_MEAN: 23.1 MAX_MED: 32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dinotefuran

CHID: 34549 CASRN: 165252-70-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K08

M4ID: 30009009 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	43.9	1.91	0.988
sd:	27.3	0.604	0.551

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	66.1	2.23	0.91	2.48	4.23
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	870.58	823.3	827.01
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	32.75	30.96	30.94

MAX_MEAN: 35.5 MAX_MED: 31.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Penoxsulam
 CHID: 34803 CASRN: 219714-96-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C18
 M4ID: 30008444

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 52.3 1.47 0.3
 sd: 98.1 5.73 0.528

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 58 1.69 0.3 4.06 0.697
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	855.44	647.41	651.17
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	25.95	8.48	8.46

MAX_MEAN: 40 MAX_MED: 38.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pentyl butyrate

CHID: 41604 CASRN: 540-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A04

M4ID: 30008506

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.4	0.995	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	20.8	1.4	0.3	4.3	4.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	726.8	639.39	643.5
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	13.09	7.85	7.86

MAX_MEAN: 17 MAX_MED: 15.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Isobornyl propanoate

CHID: 42062 CASRN: 2756-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L11

M4ID: 30009036

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19.8	2.07	1.49
sd:	10.2	0.34	0.727

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.8	2.07	1.49	3.93	9.18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.06	484.8	488.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.23	4.61	4.61

MAX_MEAN: 14.3 MAX_MED: 12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dibutyl nonanedioate

CHID: 44815 CASRN: 2917-73-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A02

M4ID: 30008771

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.4	0.777	0.3
sd:	13.1	2.63	0.336

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.5	0.778	0.3	4.18	1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	670.89	476.56	480.47
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.11	3.26	3.26

MAX_MEAN: 12.7 MAX_MED: 12.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: CI-1044

CHID: 47291 CASRN: NOCAS_47291

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G08

M4ID: 30008328

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	27.8	2.1	0.548
sd:	6.97	0.385	0.126

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.8	2.1	0.548	4.3	4.43
sd:	6.96	0.385	0.126	1870	4130

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	673.75	518.79	522.79
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.71	3.93	3.93

MAX_MEAN: 17.9 MAX_MED: 17.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dexamethasone sodium phosphate

CHID: 47429 CASRN: 2392-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H05

M4ID: 30008934

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31	2.75	0.845
sd:	40.2	1.02	0.321

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.9	2.3	0.979	2.99	10.6
sd:	15.9	0.683	0.39	327	5050

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	573.21	540.51	544.95
PROB:	0	0.9	0.1
RMSE:	6.39	4.97	4.98

MAX_MEAN: 10.3 MAX_MED: 11.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48507

CHID: 48507 CASRN: NOCAS_48507

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I13

M4ID: 30008966

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.7	1.9	1.9
sd:	2.15	0.0832	0.448

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.9	1.96	1.8	2.58	3.88
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.58	421.38	425.33
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.98	2.32	2.32

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 13.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48509

CHID: 48509 CASRN: NOCAS_48509

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B15

M4ID: 30008471

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	67.8	1.93	0.679
sd:	19	0.377	0.136

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	67.7	1.91	0.7	2.38	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	841.98	578.68	582.35
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	24.8	5.61	5.61

MAX_MEAN: 43.6 MAX_MED: 42 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 17alpha-Ethinylestradiol
 CHID: 20576 CASRN: 57-63-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J08
 M4ID: 30008985

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.44e-09 -1.05 7.93
 sd: 9.58e-05 1460 248000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 20 -3.7 4.74 0.143 2
 sd: 2.88 51 242 0.18 0.705

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	753	759	713.23
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	15.72	15.72	11.81

MAX_MEAN: 23 MAX_MED: 19.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 49 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butylparaben

CHID: 20209 CASRN: 94-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B17

M4ID: 30008521

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	137	0.71	3.38
sd:	6.32	0.0508	0.822

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	182	0.892	2.4	2.04	3.59
sd:	5.72	0.0217	0.204	0.0169	0.271

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1097.37	923.42	718.23
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	101.16	44.16	15.55

MAX_MEAN: 168 MAX_MED: 167 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylphenol
CHID: 20221 CASRN: 98-54-4
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B22
M4ID: 30008464

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.3	-0.032	1.23
sd:	1.67	0.355	1.23

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.9	0.254	0.694	2.28	16.6
sd:	4.85	0.546	0.539	0.0313	25.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	733.11	671.44	669.25
PROB:	0	0.25	0.75
RMSE:	13.88	9.38	9.09

MAX_MEAN: 16.6 MAX_MED: 20.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Catechol
 CHID: 20257 CASRN: 120-80-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M18
 M4ID: 30009067

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.92 2.8 7.84
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.3 1.05 8 1.73 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	596.37	602.37	496.53
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	6.76	6.76	3.49

MAX_MEAN: 14 MAX_MED: 13.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: o,p'-DDD
 CHID: 20372 CASRN: 53-19-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K19
 M4ID: 30008656

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 16.1 2.8 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 31.9 0.968 1.52 1.27 14.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	715.3	721.3	695.41
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	12.61	12.61	11.14

MAX_MEAN: 16.6 MAX_MED: 18.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10; 7

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dehydroepiandrosterone
 CHID: 20379 CASRN: 53-43-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D18
 M4ID: 30008851 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	23.3	-1.01	6.78
sd:	2.69	0.408	287

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	41.1	-0.954	7.82	1.71	4.92
sd:	2.24	0.779	134	0.0451	2.92

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	869.96	811.83	711.18
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	29.24	20.22	11.62

MAX_MEAN: 52.6 MAX_MED: 48.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Dinitrotoluene
 CHID: 20528 CASRN: 606-20-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J06
 M4ID: 30008693 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.2	0.0979	8
sd:	2.16	0.347	26.6

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	69.7	0.52	3.01	1.04	16.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	866.66	842.56	808.5
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	35.25	31.95	22.68

MAX_MEAN: 64.8 MAX_MED: 56.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Hexylresorcinol
 CHID: 20699 CASRN: 136-77-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A03
 M4ID: 30008772 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	20.1	2.8	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	29.3	0.0885	7.81	0.935	17.4
sd:	6.69	7.18	634	1.03	274

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	872.08	878.08	864.66
PROB:	0.02	0	0.97
RMSE:	32.79	32.79	31.39

MAX_MEAN: 29.5 MAX_MED: 26.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 10; 7

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Picloram

CHID: 21160 CASRN: 1918-02-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K18

M4ID: 30009019

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	26.1	0.63	8
sd:	1.27	0.0762	21.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	56.1	1.04	1.32	1.95	1.24
sd:	16.8	0.179	0.285	0.183	0.299

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	824.02	653.56	618.73
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	22.24	9.07	7.58

MAX_MEAN: 39.8 MAX_MED: 38.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

-56
-65

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,2',6,6'-Tetrachlorobisphenol A
 CHID: 21770 CASRN: 79-95-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K15
 M4ID: 30008660 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0973	2.8	7.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	28.8	0.764	6.88	1.01	17.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	685.97	691.97	666.61
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	13.74	13.74	12.51

MAX_MEAN: 17.8 MAX_MED: 17.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10; 7

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5alpha-Dihydrotestosterone

CHID: 22364 CASRN: 521-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C11

M4ID: 30008820

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.9	-1.01	7.36
sd:	1.6	0.533	439

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	51.3	-0.731	1.76	0.626	0.348
sd:	42.6	0.443	2.12	1.97	0.189

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	809.64	720.11	701.35
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	20.44	12.13	11.08

MAX_MEAN: 30.4 MAX_MED: 30.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexylparaben
CHID: 22525 CASRN: 5153-25-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L11
M4ID: 30008640

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.2	-0.961	7.17
sd:	7.92	8.38	1530

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	99.3	0.319	1.31	1.62	18
sd:	11.8	0.148	0.483	0.391	89.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	991.85	993.5	878.64
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	56.02	53.66	29.2

MAX_MEAN: 93.7 MAX_MED: 89.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Butyl glycidyl ether

CHID: 24691 CASRN: 2426-08-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B09

M4ID: 30008529

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	44.2	0.911	2.11
sd:	1.33	0.0304	0.254

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	69.7	1.14	1.51	2.26	1.08
sd:	20.3	0.125	0.2	0.231	0.423

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	889.21	605.81	573.33
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	31.55	7.35	5.78

MAX_MEAN: 50.1 MAX_MED: 50.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 6-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl disulfide

CHID: 25429 CASRN: 6088-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D13

M4ID: 30008846

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	27.1	1.15	3.28
sd:	1.44	0.0463	0.835

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	57.9	1.28	2.71	1.89	0.558
sd:	36	0.0779	0.556	0.951	0.297

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	800.05	626.41	623.49
PROB:	0	0.19	0.81
RMSE:	20.24	8.01	7.9

MAX_MEAN: 34.7 MAX_MED: 33.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: (2Z)-3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-ol

CHID: 26728 CASRN: 106-25-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B18

M4ID: 30008468

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30.7	-0.43	0.76
sd:	2.02	0.215	0.277

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	31.7	-0.0122	7.95	2.28	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	865.4	695.16	667.76
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	27.16	10.99	8.79

MAX_MEAN: 40.7 MAX_MED: 39.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Nilutamide

CHID: 34165 CASRN: 63612-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L06

M4ID: 30008645

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	84.1	2.45	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	26.6	1.29	3.21	1.54	15.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	731.88	736.77	730.43
PROB:	0.32	0.03	0.65
RMSE:	20.43	20.2	20.14

MAX_MEAN: 11.6 MAX_MED: 13.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 0.68

FLAGS: 10; 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 1-Hydroxypyrene
 CHID: 38298 CASRN: 5315-79-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H20
 M4ID: 30008727 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.39	2.8	7.95
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	37.5	1.25	1.86	1.5	18
sd:	38.1	0.488	1.22	0.605	54.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	763.09	769.09	730.54
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	21.49	21.49	20.18

MAX_MEAN: 21.7 MAX_MED: 21.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10; 7

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benodanil

CHID: 41623 CASRN: 15310-01-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D15

M4ID: 30008848

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.3	0.803	2.19
sd:	0.902	0.0577	0.413

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	45.1	1.31	1.32	1.92	1.67
sd:	13.6	0.168	0.198	0.119	0.272

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	750.03	556.7	499.99
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	14.88	5.47	3.77

MAX_MEAN: 28.8 MAX_MED: 29.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 5HPP-33

CHID: 46970 CASRN: 105624-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N02

M4ID: 30008601

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.2	-0.0571	8
sd:	1.43	0.55	76.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	28.3	0.01	7.97	1.84	3.73
sd:	1.73	0.0814	63.3	0.0367	1.02

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1058.47	944.88	860.02
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	19.34	11.81	8.37

MAX_MEAN: 28.8 MAX_MED: 31.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: SR271425

CHID: 47347 CASRN: 155990-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J04

M4ID: 30008695

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	37.1	2.72	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	47.4	1.3	1.77	1.91	12.9
sd:	8.62	0.127	0.523	0.0101	4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	772.36	735.23	607.02
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	19.42	14.93	7.24

MAX_MEAN: 44.6 MAX_MED: 40.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 3-Hydroxyfluorene

CHID: 47540 CASRN: 6344-67-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C20

M4ID: 30008442 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	20.5	2.8	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	24	0.665	8	1.75	18
sd:	2.36	0.0756	8.85	0.0845	23.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	783.92	789.93	715.22
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	18.79	18.79	13.68

MAX_MEAN: 28.1 MAX_MED: 25.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2-Aminoanthraquinone
 CHID: 20068 CASRN: 117-79-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D15
 M4ID: 30008423

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	62.9	0.401	1.5
sd:	3.01	0.0921	0.295

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	126	0.973	0.961	1.98	1.43
sd:	35.8	0.238	0.188	0.144	0.362

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	981.7	807.55	773.88
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	52.74	25.59	19.16

MAX_MEAN: 84.9 MAX_MED: 90.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol dibromide

CHID: 20164 CASRN: 3296-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I12

M4ID: 30008711

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.1	0.892	1.66
sd:	2.15	0.0668	0.451

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	77.2	1.35	1.09	2.05	0.883
sd:	59.3	0.431	0.385	0.631	0.539

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	855.54	666.98	663.27
PROB:	0	0.14	0.86
RMSE:	26.77	9.63	9.68

MAX_MEAN: 37.7 MAX_MED: 37.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Blue 74

CHID: 20190 CASRN: 860-22-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091019

M4ID: 30008336

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	41.3	1.68	0.931
sd:	5.58	0.153	0.161

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	44.9	1.72	0.994	2.35	18
sd:	6.69	0.141	0.122	0.00887	5.85

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	787.73	529.56	526.19
PROB:	0	0.16	0.84
RMSE:	18.44	4.21	4.03

MAX_MEAN: 33 MAX_MED: 32.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Propyl gallate
 CHID: 21201 CASRN: 121-79-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B12
 M4ID: 30008474

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	20.3	2.8	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	43.3	2.3	8	3.09	11.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	701.71	688.72	682.92
PROB:	0	0.05	0.95
RMSE:	11.63	10.44	9.49

MAX_MEAN: 21.3 MAX_MED: 24.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octanal

CHID: 21643 CASRN: 124-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E18

M4ID: 30008396

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	24.8	1.78	0.534
sd:	14	0.965	0.239

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	28.3	1.89	0.575	2.33	17.9
sd:	11.1	0.57	0.138	0.0144	11.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	681.56	516.61	516
PROB:	0	0.42	0.58
RMSE:	10.22	4.28	4.07

MAX_MEAN: 17.6 MAX_MED: 18.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-(2-Methylbutan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 21771 CASRN: 80-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A18

M4ID: 30008492

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	23.7	-2.73	7.02
sd:	2.08	0.173	36.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	63.5	-0.373	0.3	1.48	1.45
sd:	19.9	0.964	0.091	0.12	0.256

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	870.49	789.91	725.56
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	28.16	18.24	13.26

MAX_MEAN: 44.4 MAX_MED: 45.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diethyl phthalate

CHID: 21780 CASRN: 84-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J16

M4ID: 30008993

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.2	1.74	1.63
sd:	2.05	0.0908	0.371

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	21.9	1.9	1.54	2.33	18
sd:	11.1	0.272	0.346	0.0177	15.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	632.53	480.37	480.35
PROB:	0	0.5	0.5
RMSE:	7.91	3.24	3.16

MAX_MEAN: 13.9 MAX_MED: 13.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzophenone

CHID: 21961 CASRN: 119-61-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D18

M4ID: 30008420

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.95	-2.11	0.3
sd:	2.15	1.23	0.194

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.7	0.0846	0.3	2.14	17.9
sd:	15.6	3.05	0.479	0.115	13.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	698.96	616.06	580.48
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	11.33	7.7	6.31

MAX_MEAN: 18.8 MAX_MED: 16.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 4-Hexyloxyaniline

CHID: 22288 CASRN: 39905-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P02

M4ID: 30008553

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	23.8	1.74	1.18
sd:	2.88	0.112	0.189

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	29.2	1.88	1.18	2.35	14.9
sd:	6.48	0.162	0.162	0.0152	6.93

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	917.9	657.6	656.29
PROB:	0	0.34	0.66
RMSE:	10.69	3.44	3.36

MAX_MEAN: 19.9 MAX_MED: 20.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Vinclozolin

CHID: 22361 CASRN: 50471-44-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F22

M4ID: 30008903

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19.1	1.76	1.28
sd:	3.17	0.136	0.254

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.9	2.01	1.14	2.33	18
sd:	12.3	0.304	0.207	0.0105	10.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	645.37	444.91	444.53
PROB:	0	0.45	0.55
RMSE:	8.69	2.69	2.7

MAX_MEAN: 16.3 MAX_MED: 15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Progesterone
CHID: 22370 CASRN: 57-83-0
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M06
M4ID: 30008621

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.299	2.8	7.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.4	1.05	0.353	1.67	18
sd:	15.8	1.41	0.161	0.0507	29.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	702.88	708.88	628.99
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	11.24	11.24	7.82

MAX_MEAN: 17 MAX_MED: 15.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Bisphenol B

CHID: 22442 CASRN: 77-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P10

M4ID: 30008797

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.00562	2.79	7.42
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	42.2	0.165	0.429	0.486	6.42
sd:	47.2	2.11	0.274	0.7	38.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	732.65	738.65	711.5
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	13.54	13.54	11.4

MAX_MEAN: 20.8 MAX_MED: 19.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10; 7

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzyl salicylate

CHID: 24598 CASRN: 118-58-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F07

M4ID: 30008383

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	46	1.6	1.13
sd:	5.65	0.122	0.203

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	58.9	1.79	1.05	2.33	18
sd:	13.8	0.195	0.155	0.0106	7.65

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	818.37	592.84	589.79
PROB:	0	0.18	0.82
RMSE:	22.23	6.37	5.98

MAX_MEAN: 40.4 MAX_MED: 43.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Acetyl tributyl citrate

CHID: 26446 CASRN: 77-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H16

M4ID: 30008731

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.57	-3.7	7.05
sd:	0.641	261	1840

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.3	0.966	0.3	1.73	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	622.12	586.67	521.17
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.14	5.7	4.05

MAX_MEAN: 10.9 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl monooleate

CHID: 27875 CASRN: 25496-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P22

M4ID: 30008785

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	11.1	0.952	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16	1.84	0.3	2.3	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	601.03	435.21	419.1
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	6.24	2.63	2.33

MAX_MEAN: 9.68 MAX_MED: 10.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Dipentyl phthalate
 CHID: 31131 CASRN: 131-18-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N20
 M4ID: 30008359

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.89	0.354	0.809
sd:	0.837	0.175	0.387

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.9	1.21	0.489	2.37	1.35
sd:	6.94	0.764	0.196	0.186	0.588

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	620.97	451.8	447.9
PROB:	0	0.12	0.88
RMSE:	6.97	2.74	2.64

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fenhexamid
 CHID: 32549 CASRN: 126833-17-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E20
 M4ID: 30008394

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.93 -0.349 0.362
 sd: 4.79 1.48 0.417

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 33.8 1.55 0.696 1.8 15.3
 sd: 26.5 0.916 0.356 0.0865 13.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	735.61	711.54	703.66
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	14.56	13.06	12.58

MAX_MEAN: 15.9 MAX_MED: 22.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Haloperidol

CHID: 34150 CASRN: 52-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A14

M4ID: 30008496

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.71	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.4	0.413	0.3	2.02	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	682.8	578.33	577.24
PROB:	0	0.37	0.63
RMSE:	9.86	6.52	5.92

MAX_MEAN: 13.4 MAX_MED: 13.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Fluroxypyr-meptyl

CHID: 34303 CASRN: 81406-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A21

M4ID: 30008544

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	22.8	1.33	0.321
sd:	13.1	1.66	0.198

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	30.4	1.68	0.429	2.32	3.02
sd:	10.3	0.654	0.117	0.0597	1.45

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	714.77	550.91	539.83
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	11.89	4.83	4.49

MAX_MEAN: 18.4 MAX_MED: 18.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: 2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxybenzophenone
 CHID: 41306 CASRN: 131-55-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F11
 M4ID: 30008892

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 14.2 2.44 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 28.5 1.64 1.05 1.89 18
 sd: 52 1.49 1.09 0.0315 25.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	710.89	705.29	703.61
PROB:	0.02	0.3	0.69
RMSE:	13.15	12.04	11.46

MAX_MEAN: 15.6 MAX_MED: 14.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 10; 7

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Benzyl cinnamate

CHID: 41663 CASRN: 103-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B20

M4ID: 30008466

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	42.1	1.45	0.977
sd:	3.34	0.0932	0.134

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	54.1	1.71	0.829	2.35	15.9
sd:	10.7	0.221	0.12	0.0088	5.11

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	824.25	521.67	518.93
PROB:	0	0.2	0.8
RMSE:	22.26	4.24	3.99

MAX_MEAN: 38.1 MAX_MED: 39.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Diphenylmercury(II)

CHID: 42130 CASRN: 587-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E12

M4ID: 30008402

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.22	-2.7	5.38
sd:	0.513	0.296	304

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.3	0.92	0.341	1.8	3.26
sd:	6.81	0.874	0.104	0.0545	0.71

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	632.28	549.61	488.72
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.53	4.88	3.31

MAX_MEAN: 12.1 MAX_MED: 12.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: HMR1426

CHID: 47338 CASRN: 262376-75-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B04

M4ID: 30008482

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.3	1.82	0.3
sd:	24.9	4.08	0.336

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	24.6	2.06	0.429	2.31	11
sd:	19.8	1.5	0.165	0.025	30.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	671.94	570.27	565.61
PROB:	0	0.09	0.91
RMSE:	9.58	5.66	5.5

MAX_MEAN: 13 MAX_MED: 12.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2493 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_dn)

NAME: Octylparaben

CHID: 47957 CASRN: 1219-38-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B02

M4ID: 30008484

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	101	1.36	1.64
sd:	3.01	0.0305	0.132

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	137	1.62	1.18	2.34	13
sd:	12	0.0822	0.0984	0.00417	2.24

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1330.21	887.37	838.39
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	59.21	9.61	7.64

MAX_MEAN: 102 MAX_MED: 99.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: